

1 Critically important, yet forgotten: thin and transient meltwater layers
2 and false bottoms in the Arctic sea ice pack

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53 Abstract

54 The rapid melt of snow and sea ice during the Arctic summer provides a significant source of low-salinity
55 meltwater to the surface ocean on the local scale. The accumulation of this meltwater on, under, and
56 around sea ice floes can result in relatively thin meltwater layers in the upper ocean. Due to the small-
57 scale nature of these upper-ocean features, typically on the order of 1 m thick or less, they are rarely
58 detected by standard methods, but are nevertheless pervasive and critically important in Arctic summer.
59 Observations during the Multidisciplinary drifting Observatory for the Study of Arctic Climate
60 (MOSAiC) expedition in summer 2020 focused on the evolution of such layers and made significant
61 advancements in understanding their role in the coupled Arctic system. Here we provide a review of thin
62 meltwater layers in the Arctic, with emphasis on the new findings from MOSAiC. Both prior and recent
63 observational datasets indicate an intermittent yet long-lasting (weeks to months) meltwater layer in the
64 upper ocean on the order of 0.1 to 1.0 m in thickness, with a large spatial range. The presence of
65 meltwater layers impacts the physical system by reducing bottom ice melt and allowing new ice
66 formation via false bottom growth. Collectively, the meltwater layer and false bottoms reduce
67 atmosphere-ocean exchanges of momentum, energy, and material. The impacts on the coupled Arctic
68 system are far-reaching, including acting as a barrier for nutrient and gas exchange and impacting
69 ecosystem diversity and productivity.

70 1. Introduction

71
72 Sea ice is an expansive cover on much of the Arctic Ocean, but in the vertical dimension it is
73 only a relatively thin veneer separating the often-deep ocean below from the atmosphere above.
74 Despite this discrepancy between horizontal and vertical scales, sea ice has far-reaching impacts

75 on the Arctic system. This paper explores a similarly thin yet impactful feature that often evades
76 our measurements — thin layers of meltwater that pool under, around, and on sea ice during the
77 melt season. Compared to their sea ice precursor, meltwater layers under sea ice and in leads are
78 challenging to visually identify and have thus been often overlooked in observations and
79 analyses of Arctic processes.

80

81 Unlike other oceans, the Arctic Ocean is predominantly stratified by salinity rather than
82 temperature (Carmack, 2007). This allows fresher waters to remain relatively undiluted near the
83 surface with more saline water masses below. On the basin scale, large freshwater fluxes are
84 provided by Arctic rivers as well as inflows from Pacific and even Atlantic Oceans (Carmack,
85 2000). Locally, however, summer sea ice and snow melt provide a significant freshwater flux.
86 This can result in notably thin layers of meltwater right at the interface between the ocean and
87 the overlying atmosphere and sea ice.

88

89 Since the first recorded observation of a meltwater layer by Fridtjof Nansen in 1894 (Nansen,
90 1902), such features have been the subject of sporadic observation across the Arctic pack ice.
91 Their presence is often overlooked due to the disconnect in scales with those that are typically
92 measured in the ocean, often beginning meters below the surface. When observed, the critical
93 importance of these layers in the Arctic climate system has been acknowledged (e.g., Vihma et
94 al., 2014). Such meltwater stratification in the upper ocean has the potential to impact many
95 physical, biological and biogeochemical processes occurring near the air-ice-ocean interface,
96 including species diversity, distribution, and productivity. Further, meltwater layers can act as a
97 barrier to air-sea gas exchange and inhibit sympagic-pelagic nutrient exchange.

98

99 The sparsity of observations of this layer and differences in terminology used by different
100 disciplines has prevented a comprehensive view of the role of sea ice and snow meltwater layers
101 in the Arctic system. This overview aims to provide a comprehensive summary of prior
102 observations and works describing the presence and implications of these layers. Our review will
103 include the results from a new set of inter-disciplinary observations and studies from the
104 Multidisciplinary drifting Observatory for the Study of Arctic Climate (MOSAiC) that were, in
105 part, designed to understand these features and their implications.

106

107 We start by defining the terminology that will be used for the meltwater layers discussed in
108 Section 2, followed by a summary of observational methods in Section 3. Our review then
109 proceeds with a short overview of the MOSAiC expedition in Section 4, which provides many
110 new insights on meltwater layers reviewed herein. We then describe the key features of the
111 physical evolution and previous observations of thin meltwater layers in Section 5, and proceed
112 through sections reviewing the implications of thin meltwater layers for different components of
113 the Arctic system. These include sea ice, ocean, organism diversity and community structure,
114 and biogeochemical gradients and air-sea exchanges across meltwater layer interfaces in
115 Sections 6-9, respectively. We conclude with perspectives on the expected impacts of climate
116 change in Section 10, and highlight key challenges and propose future directions for this area of
117 research in Section 11.

118

119
 120 **Figure 1. Schematic of thin meltwater layer locations in sea ice-covered regions.** Thin, meltwater layers can occur
 121 in melt ponds, under the ice, and in leads. Schematic also shows the key drivers in the physical evolution of layers,
 122 with ecological and biogeochemical implications summarized in **Figure 12** below. Not to scale. Figure by Madison
 123 Smith & Natalie Renier © Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution

124 2. Terminology

125 This manuscript focuses on the evolution and implications of thin meltwater layers that form in
 126 the Arctic Ocean during the melt season. We define thin meltwater layers as relatively shallow –
 127 on the order 0.1 to 1.0 m – layers of relatively low salinity < 20 g/kg. These layers have also
 128 been referred to in the literature and by the community as “freshwater lenses” and “freshwater
 129 layers”, but it should be noted that they are not strictly fresh water. Meltwater is used here to
 130 distinguish the freshwater as locally-derived from in situ melt, rather than from other sources
 131 such as terrestrial/riverine input or land ice melt inflows. Based on the vertical scale of focus
 132 here, these meltwater layers are also distinct from larger-scale meltwater-freshened mixed layers
 133 such as in Crews et al. (2022). The possibility of meltwater layers on the 0.1 - 1.0-m scale in the
 134 Southern Ocean is not discussed here, but, to our knowledge, they have not been previously
 135 documented in Antarctic sea ice.

136
 137 Snow- and ice meltwater can be conceptualized as spreading across the heterogenous sea ice
 138 cover in a thin layer, thus including three primary locations: melt ponds, under-ice meltwater
 139 layers also known as under-ice melt ponds, and lead meltwater layers between floes (**Figure 1**).
 140 Melt ponds are included in the definition here as an important sink in the meltwater budget
 141 where stratification can occur, but the focus in this review is on the unique and less well-
 142 described presence of meltwater layers between and underneath sea ice floes. It is not uncommon
 143 for meltwater in leads and under ice to refreeze at the interface with the colder and saltier ocean
 144 water below. This is most commonly observed below the ice, where the refrozen layer is referred
 145 to as a false bottom. Other possible sinks of meltwater include refreezing in voids within ridge
 146 keels or at the base of lead meltwater layers (**Figure 1**). False bottoms have not been included
 147 previously in the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) Sea Ice Nomenclature (JCOMM

148 Expert Team on Sea Ice, 2014), but have been proposed for inclusion in future versions due to
149 the increasing capability to observe this common sub-surface feature.

150

151 *Table 1. Definitions of meltwater layer locations and associated features.*

	Definition
Melt ponds	The pooling of snow and sea ice meltwater on the surface of the sea ice. Ponds can either be connected to the ocean below or separated from the ocean below by impermeable sea ice or a ‘false bottom’. Also referred to as melt puddles (JCOMM Expert Team on Sea Ice, 2014).
Under-ice meltwater layers	Thin meltwater layers that occur below the sea ice. Analogous to melt ponds in that they are topographically constrained and contain meltwater. Also referred to as under-ice melt ponds.
Lead meltwater layers	Thin meltwater layers in leads or cracks between floes.
False bottoms	Ice growth vertically separated from the main ice floe by a liquid void. Typically forms during the melt season at the base of under-ice meltwater layers in contact with cold, ambient seawater or at the base of a drainage hole where a melt pond connects to the ocean surface layer below.

152

153 3. Sampling and observational techniques

154 Limited methods are available for sampling and observing meltwater layers under and
155 surrounding sea ice. Traditional profiling CTDs (conductivity, temperature, and depth
156 instruments), whether free-falling or deployed by winch, are unable to fully resolve thin
157 meltwater layers due to the minimum required averaging interval of tens of centimeters. These
158 features typically cannot be observed from ships due to the mixing of the upper water column by
159 the ship’s wake. Additionally, temperature and conductivity sensors on CTD rosette samplers are
160 usually mounted at the bottom, such that the shallowest measurable depth is around 1 m. These
161 measurement limitations have further implications for the ability to identify associated changes
162 in ecological and biogeochemical parameters on the relevant scale, where low salinity layers are
163 easily mixed and disturbed.

164

165 The majority of observations of under-ice and lead meltwater layers have come from on-ice point
166 measurements of water properties. The lowering of a probe to collect in situ point measurements
167 of temperature and salinity has been employed in leads (Nansen, 1902; Perovich and Maykut
168 1990; Richter-Menge, et al., 2001; Pegau et al., 2002) and under-ice (e.g., Smith et al., 2022).
169 Observations of under-ice meltwater were typically done through collection of water either using
170 a pump (Eicken, 1994) or by SCUBA divers (Ehn et al., 2011); the water is subsequently
171 measured for salinity using a conductivity probe or salinometer (where if salinity is reported on
172 the practical salinity scale the values are dimensionless, whereas absolute salinity is reported in
173 g/kg). Profiling measurements from a hole in drifting sea ice using buoyant, ascending profilers,
174 such as the vertical microstructure profiler (VMP) (Fer et al., 2022b), can resolve the meltwater
175 layer with minimal disturbance to the water structure. Recent developments in equipping

176 remotely operated vehicles (ROV) with CTD sensors allow fine scale and high vertical
177 resolution profiles directly under sea ice (Katlein et al., 2017).

178
179 Under-ice meltwater layers have been indicated using measurements of temperature, such as
180 from active profiling or buoys with thermistor chains (Langleben, 1966; Provost et al., 2019; Lei
181 et al., 2022). However, the lack of conductivity/salinity observations creates challenges in
182 differentiating meltwater from ice (Lei et al., 2022), as estimates from temperature alone are
183 ambiguous. Sea ice drilling, such as for measuring thickness and coring, can be a reliable, yet
184 destructive, method to determine the presence of false bottoms. In addition to false bottoms
185 serving as a concrete indicator of relatively fresh meltwater, the desalinization of the bottom of
186 the ice core can indicate prior under-ice meltwater layers (Eicken, 1994). Similarly, the ease of
187 drilling can serve as a qualitative indicator of prior meltwater layers since fresher ice is harder to
188 drill through than more saline ice. The presence of under-ice meltwater layers and associated
189 false bottoms have also been qualitatively assessed visually using imagery (Assmy et al., 2013;
190 Perovich, personal communication, 2022) and from under-ice sonar data (Wang et al., 2013
191 Salganik et al., in review). At present, thin meltwater features and false bottoms cannot be
192 observed by airborne or satellite remote sensing as these features cannot be detected through sea
193 ice and meltwater layers in leads typically occur on a smaller spatial scale than can be resolved.

194
195 Relative to under-ice and lead meltwater layers, methods to measure melt ponds are relatively
196 straightforward, and the observational record of melt ponds extends as far back as the 1950s
197 (e.g., Nazintsev, 1964). Given the extensive field of research on melt ponds, a complete
198 description of melt pond properties and processes is beyond the scope of this review. Instead, we
199 refer readers to the cited references for more information on melt pond observations (Fetterer and
200 Untersteiner, 1998; Yackel et al., 2000; Perovich et al., 2001, 2002; Eicken et al., 2002, 2004;
201 Scharien et al., 2005; Petrich et al., 2012; Polashenski et al., 2012, 2017; Rösel et al., 2012;
202 Webster et al., 2015, 2022; Istomina et al., 2015; Buckley et al., 2020; Wright and Polashenski,
203 2018, Wright et al., 2020), and highlight the key linkages that melt ponds have with other
204 meltwater layers.

205
206 Melt ponds undergo different stages of evolution as melt progresses: (1) initial formation and
207 growth, during which the surface of ponds can be above sea level, (2) vertical drainage due to
208 permeable ice and/or macroscopic flaws within the sea-ice structure, draining ponds to sea level
209 (3) continued deepening of ponds, at which points thaw holes form and pond floors melt through,
210 and (4) either complete melt-out or refreezing. Prior to Stage 2, the size (or areal extent) and
211 depth of a melt pond are adequate for estimating the meltwater content within a given pond. Melt
212 pond depth can be measured through a variety of methods, including manual measurements with
213 a marked ski pole or ruler (e.g., Perovich et al., 2003; Polashenski et al., 2015) or using an
214 automated depth probe (Webster et al., 2022), all of which tend to have an uncertainty of 1 cm or
215 less. Recently, pond depths have been derived from remotely-sensed data (e.g., König and
216 Oppelt, 2020; Farrell et al., 2020; Tilling et al., 2020; Herzfeld et al., 2022), though assessments
217 are ongoing to quantify retrieval uncertainties and biases. Melt pond size and areal coverage can
218 be quantified using high-resolution imagery from kites (e.g., Petrich et al., 2012), drones (e.g.,
219 Calmer et al., in review), aircraft (e.g., Miao et al., 2015; Buckley et al., 2020; Wright et al.,
220 2020), and satellites (e.g., Fetterer and Untersteiner, 1998; Rösel et al., 2012; Webster et al.,
221 2015; Wright and Polashenski, 2018; Niehaus et al., in review) using supervised and

222 unsupervised classification methods, including machine learning techniques. Methods to
223 estimate melt pond coverage and depth are continuing to rapidly evolve with advancing
224 technology.

225

226 4. Overview of observations on the MOSAiC expedition

227 Thin meltwater layers were observed during the course of the MOSAiC expedition, which was a
228 year-long drift expedition in the Central Arctic from October 2019 to October 2020. An
229 overview of the drift and highlights of physical evolution can be found in Nicolaus et al. (2022),
230 Shupe et al. (2022) and Rabe et al. (2022). The expedition was divided into 5 legs while
231 observations of relevance for the questions addressed here primarily derive from summer,
232 spanning June-July (Leg 4) and August-September (Leg 5). Drift tracks are shown in **Figure 2**,
233 which were spatially discontinuous due to drift of the original floe breaking up upon reaching the
234 ice edge in late July. Nevertheless, the expedition collected an unparalleled density of
235 observations of the Arctic air-ice-ocean system, measuring key parameters for nearly the entire
236 year.

237

238 The science approach utilized disciplinary teams making coordinated observations to facilitate
239 inter-disciplinary analysis and understanding. The importance of fine-scale stratification during
240 the summer melt season had been identified during planning as a key under-sampled feature
241 during the melt season. Thus, interdisciplinary sampling was undertaken to capture the
242 implications of meltwater features. In particular, coordinated sampling of leads with semi-
243 continuous and discrete observations made by sea ice (Nicolaus et al., 2022), ocean (Rabe et al.,
244 2022), atmosphere (Shupe et al., 2022), ecology (Fong et al., in prep), and biogeochemistry
245 teams (Damm et al., in prep) were undertaken during both Legs 4 and 5 (**Figure 2**). These
246 dedicated observations provide the most complete picture of meltwater layer processes that exist,
247 while numerous other sensors provide opportunistic and supplementary insight into evolution
248 and implications of meltwater layers.

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250

251

252 **Figure 2. Maps of MOSAiC meltwater layer sampling areas.** a) Drift tracks of MOSAiC Legs 4 (June 18 – July 29;
253 magenta) and 5 (August 20 – September 20; red). Blue to white shading shows the average July 2020 ice
254 concentration. Aerial imagery of floes (Neckel, et al., 2022) indicate primary lead sampling sites with stars and
255 melt pond sampling sites with circles for b) Leg 4 and c) Leg 5.

256 The summer conditions during the MOSAiC expedition can be considered anomalous in terms of
257 air temperature and typical in terms of wind speeds (Rinke et al., 2021). The July and August
258 conditions at the moving position of MOSAiC were among the warmest in the climatology
259 (1979-2020), with temperature being above the 75th percentile of climatological records 52% and

260 60% of the time in July and August, respectively. These anomalous temperatures are likely
261 related to the fact that the expedition was closer to the ice edge than it would have been at the
262 same location earlier in the climatological period due to the low summer ice extent (Rinke et al.,
263 2021). In contrast, wind speeds at 10-m height in July were nearly perfectly aligned with
264 historical distributions, with 26% both above and below the interquartile range of the
265 climatology. August and September wind speeds were slightly anomalously low with 32% and
266 30% below 25th percentile, respectively (Rinke et al., 2021).

267 5. Physical evolution of thin meltwater layers

268 The first recorded observation of thin, meltwater layers in leads or cracks was made by Nansen
269 during the drift of Fram in 1894 (Nansen, 1902; **Figure 3**). He described a “nearly fresh layer of
270 water [between floes], with a temperature about or even above 0°C”. The layer was
271 approximately 2 m thick on July 11, with a salinity of 1-2 and noticeable clumps of algae
272 floating near the bottom boundary of the layer (Nansen, 1902). Subsequent observations of these
273 difficult-to-observe meltwater layers below sea ice, in cracks and leads, suggest that these
274 features likely occur in the pack ice across most of the Arctic during the melt season.
275

276 While false bottoms were likely first described by Untersteiner and Badgley (1958), Hanson
277 (1965) provides the first detailed quantification of associated under-ice meltwater layers or
278 “under-ice melt ponds”. Under-ice meltwater layers, inferred by the presence of false bottoms
279 below, were observed with ablation stakes at sites near both a natural and artificial drainage hole
280 in the Chukchi Sea in 1958 (Hanson, 1965). The superposition of two meltwater layers and false
281 bottoms infers two subsequent drainage events prior to observation, after which the layers and
282 false bottoms gradually thinned through August and into September, when observations ceased.
283 In 1965 in the Canadian Arctic (Ellesmere Island), the temperature evolution of a likely low-
284 salinity under-ice meltwater layer was more directly measured during the melt season, with water
285 temperature increasing from -1.4 to -0.4°C (Langleben, 1966). Unpublished observations from
286 the Fram Strait in July 1984 showed qualitative evidence of a meltwater layer formed beneath
287 the ice during a calm period, resulting in the growth of platelet ice (**Figure 4**)**Error! Reference**
288 **source not found.**, that was mixed away once the winds increased (D. Perovich, personal
289 communication, 2022). While submarine sonar measurements indicated that under-ice meltwater
290 layers may be common under the Arctic ice pack (Wadhams and Martin, 1990), Perovich and
291 Maykut (1990) documented the development of a warm, relatively fresh layer in a stable lead
292 with an initial width of 3 m during summer of 1982 in the Canadian Arctic (Mould Bay). By July
293 6, there was an approximately 2 m thick, well-mixed, relatively fresh (practical salinity ~ 3)
294 surface layer which warmed over mid-July to a maximum temperature above 0°C. Horizontal
295 variations in the lead temperature structure were small. During the Surface Heat Budget in the
296 Arctic Ocean (SHEBA) study in the Beaufort Sea in 1998, a stable lead developed a strongly-
297 stratified, relatively fresh meltwater layer (practical salinity < 4) down to a maximum depth of 1.4
298 m around July 25 (Richter-Menge et al., 2001), with the highest fraction of this meltwater
299 coming from surface snow and ice melt (Perovich et al., 2021). In addition, Pegau (2002)
300 described the effect of this thin lead meltwater layer on light attenuation and absorption during
301 SHEBA. A helicopter survey (July 22) of 8 additional leads around the SHEBA camp showed
302 that thin (< 1.5 m) low-salinity (practical salinity < 10) lead meltwater layers were present in all of
303 them (Richter-Menge et al., 2001). Meltwater layers in cracks and ice holes were indicated by

304 observations in the Eastern Central Arctic in 2012 by visual imagery of density gradients and the
 305 presence of floating algal aggregates at the meltwater-saltwater interface (Assmy et al., 2013). In
 306 contrast to these observations, leads in the Arctic under stormier conditions have been observed
 307 to remain well-mixed throughout the summer melt season (e.g., McPhee et al., 1987).
 308

309 A more detailed investigation of under-ice meltwater layers was completed in the Central Arctic
 310 in 1991 (Eicken, 1994), with meltwater layers characterized by a practical salinity of 1.5
 311 reaching a thickness of 0.3 m. Using false bottoms as an indication of the lower-bound of
 312 coverage of under-ice meltwater layers, they occurred under approximately 10% of level-ice core
 313 locations in the Beaufort Sea in 1992 and 1993 (Jeffries et al., 1995), and at least 15% of
 314 observed locations in the Beaufort Sea during SHEBA in 1998 (Perovich et al., 2003).
 315 Observations under landfast sea ice in the Amundsen Gulf, in the Canadian Arctic, indicated
 316 evolution of a 0.5-m thick meltwater layer over June 2008 (Ehn et al., 2011; Hop et al., 2011;
 317 Mundy et al., 2011). Measurements showed practical salinities less than 10 on two of the three
 318 observation dates, with the meltwater layer generally becoming thicker and more saline over the
 319 sampling period (Mundy et al., 2011). Meltwater layers in the upper few meters of the ocean
 320 were inferred from ship-based measurements in late summer 2014 in the Fram Strait, where the
 321 meltwater signal was associated with an increase in light scattering (Granskog et al., 2015).
 322

323
 324 **Figure 3. Summary of key historical observations of meltwater layers.** Timing, by month, of key historical records
 325 of meltwater layers in leads (purple) and under-ice (green, with dark green being inferred from false bottoms) in the
 326 Arctic. Size of circles corresponds to the approximate maximum thickness of the observed layer in meters.

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Figure 4. Qualitative observation of under-ice meltwater layer and ice growth in Fram Strait. Platelet ice growth is observed, from below, growing at the interface of the meltwater layer and the ocean in the Fram Strait, July 1984. Such qualitative observations have been used historically to indicate presence of meltwater layers. Photo courtesy of D. Perovich.

333

334 The physical evolution of these thin meltwater layers underneath ice and in leads is determined
335 by the balance of the stratification of freshwater, reduced momentum transfer, and mixing (e.g.,
336 Smith et al., 2022). In particular, the stratification is determined by inputs of relatively fresh
337 meltwater. While sea ice melt onset can begin as early as April, meltwater input from snow and
338 sea ice in most of the Arctic begins in earnest in June (e.g., Perovich et al., 2021). Meltwater flux
339 from melting snow and ice often continues through August and sometimes September, until
340 freeze-up begins. A relatively small fraction of meltwater remains on the ice in melt ponds, while
341 a majority drains into the ocean laterally or vertically, where it may accumulate in meltwater
342 layers (Perovich et al., 2021). The majority of pond drainage occurs through horizontal transport
343 on the ice to macroscopic flaws formed from enlarged brine channels (Polashenski et al., 2012).
344 In situ precipitation in the summer is not well quantified, but likely plays a small role in the
345 freshwater budget relative to the melting of sea ice and accumulated snow. Mixing of meltwater
346 with the ocean mixed layer below is largely driven by wind and ice motion, which can result in
347 intermittent or rapid changes in stratification and presence of meltwater layers (e.g., Richter-
348 Menge et al., 2001; Smith et al., 2022; Nomura et al., in review). Shear within the ocean from
349 wind-driven ice drift may be more important than air-sea surface stress or waves for narrow
350 leads under typically light summer winds. This turbulence can propagate upwards to erode the
351 density gradient at the base of the meltwater layer.

352

353 Various modeling efforts have contributed to our understanding of the general drivers of
354 meltwater evolution in the Arctic upper ocean. A one-dimensional model applied to the upper
355 ocean of the Nansen Basin (Rudels, 2016) suggests that the under-ice meltwater layer is self-
356 sustaining by driving melt of ice. The mixed-layer models typically simulate a thicker surface
357 layer than the meltwater layers reported here (e.g., Rudels, 2016), but the implications and
358 principles of evolution will largely be the same. Maintenance of meltwater layers is a balance
359 between buoyancy, the addition of fresher meltwater and entrainment of water below by wind or
360 shear-driven mixing. Buoyancy input from above is both positive, from melting of snow and sea
361 ice, and negative, as a result of cooling and sea ice brine rejection during both ice formation and
362 melt. Floe-scale simulations using the MIT General Circulation Model (MITGCM) (Horvat, et
363 al., 2016) incorporate the horizontal mixing resulting from ocean eddies, and also simulate the
364 evolution of a relatively fresh lens beneath sea ice during the melt season. In contrast to the

365 definition of meltwater as salinity <20 g/kg used herein, the melt layers in the MITGCM study
366 had relatively small differences from the ocean below with salinity ~ 33 g/kg, but nonetheless had
367 stable enough stratification to persist across large spatial scales.

368
369 During the MOSAiC expedition, continuous observations of thin meltwater layers from melt
370 onset to freeze-up were limited by logistical constraints (Nicolaus et al., 2022) but the evolution
371 was captured by a combination of continuous and focused observation periods during July (Leg
372 4) and September (Leg 5) (**Figure 5** and **Figure 6**). Following the short-lived melt onset and
373 pond formation in late May (Cox et al., in prep; Webster et al., 2022) the formation of melt
374 ponds began in earnest in mid-June. Meltwater layers in leads and under-ice likely began
375 forming days to weeks after; the first indications of a meltwater layer in leads visually observed
376 on July 1st, with under-ice meltwater indicated by the presence of a false bottom at an
377 oceanographic observation site in late June (Schulz, et al., 2022) and at the long-term first-year
378 ice (FYI) coring site on July 6th (Salganik et al., in review). The anomalously warm conditions
379 during July and August possibly contributed to larger meltwater fluxes than might be expected in
380 earlier years in the climatological record (Rinke et al., 2021).

381
382 In **Figure 5** and **Figure 6****Figure 8**, we summarize the evolution during Legs 4 and 5 of the
383 MOSAiC expedition, respectively, of the meltwater layer in the three primary sinks as observed
384 by a variety of platforms: leads in purple, melt ponds in blue, and under-ice layers in green. The
385 average meltwater layer thickness is defined here as the depth relative to the relevant air-water or
386 ice-water interface at which the maximum change in density occurs, and the salinity is
387 characterized using the average of all available measurements above this depth, which should
388 have salinity less than 20 g/kg. This definition of meltwater layer thickness is distinct from the
389 equivalent freshwater thickness, as used in other publications (i.e., Smith et al. 2022) due to the
390 requirement of a reference ocean salinity in the latter which may evolve spatially and temporally.
391 Under-ice meltwater layer estimates come primarily from in situ profiling using a YSI
392 conductivity and temperature probe (Smith et al., 2022), ice mass balance (IMB) buoys, sea ice
393 coring, and a microstructure probe (MSS) (Schulz et al., 2022) where spatial variability in
394 locations leads to some of the temporal variability observed. Lead meltwater layer estimates
395 come primarily from in situ profiling with YSI (Smith et al., 2021), a Castaway CTD (Smith et
396 al., 2021), Fishing-Rod CTD (Karam et al. 2023), and a VMP “upriser” (Fer et al., 2022b). Melt
397 pond depths are averaged from repeated mass balance transect measurements which had slightly
398 lower pond coverage than the broader area and did not include the deepest ponds in the vicinity
399 (Webster et al., 2022). Melt pond salinities on select dates were obtained from a combination of
400 isotope samples (Lange et al., 2022) and profiles using a Rinke CTD. Due to variability in
401 measurement type, location, and interval, results are not often directly comparable. Nonetheless,
402 combining these diverse datasets gives us insight into key features of the temporal evolution.

403
404 Following the initial formation and observation of meltwater layers in leads and under-ice at the
405 beginning of July, the thickness initially increases before gradually declining (**Figure 5**) (Lei et
406 al., 2022). Salinities of meltwater layers are generally lowest in the middle of the melt season
407 when meltwater inputs are highest, gradually increasing over time as a result of mixing and
408 entrainment of ocean water from below and release of brine from the ice above. Example profiles
409 of lead meltwater layers on three dates in July (**Figure 7**) demonstrate the general trend towards
410 a thinner meltwater layer, with gradual decrease in the strength of stratification at the halocline.

411 Melt ponds represented a relatively small, but consistent, meltwater reservoir throughout much
 412 of July. The thickness of lead meltwater layers was negatively correlated with lead width as a
 413 result of conservation of volume (Nomura et al., 2022). The disappearance of meltwater layers in
 414 September was synchronous across locations of leads and melt ponds (**Figure 6**). The
 415 differences in temporal and spatial factors between the time periods make it difficult to compare,
 416 where July observations occurred on a mix of multi-year ice (MYI) and first-year ice (FYI) near
 417 Fram Strait while August to September observations occurred on FYI near the North Pole.
 418 However, the observed dissolution of the meltwater layers under-ice and in leads during both
 419 July and September correspond to the timing of anomalously high winds above the
 420 climatological 75th percentile (Rinke et al., 2021; Smith et al., 2022). Example profiles from
 421 leads on three dates from August - September (**Figure 8**) show the dissolution of stratification
 422 between 5 and 9 September following the observed storm.
 423
 424

425
 426 **Figure 5. Summary of meltwater layer physical property evolution from the MOSAiC expedition during melt**
 427 **season, July 2020.** Summary of evolution of meltwater layers physical properties during MOSAiC melt season,
 428 including average estimated thickness (a) and absolute salinity (b) of meltwater layers in leads (purple), melt ponds
 429 (blue), and under-ice (green). Meltwater layer thickness is defined here as the depth of maximum change in density.
 430 Markers indicate different measurement platforms, where circles indicate YSI probe (Smith et al., 2021), triangles
 431 are fishing-rod CTD, squares are mass-balance transects (Webster et al., 2022), x's are coring observations (Smith
 432 et al., 2022; Salganik et al., in revision), stars are from the MSS profiler where an approximate ice thickness of 2 m
 433 was assumed (Schulz et al., 2022), and dashed lines are estimates from IMB using mass balance calculations
 434 (Salganik et al., in revision). Vertical grey dashed lines correspond to dates of profiles in **Figure 7**.

435

436

437

438 **Figure 6. Summary of meltwater layer physical property evolution from the MOSAiC expedition during freeze-**
 439 **up, August-September 2020.** Summary of evolution of meltwater layers physical properties during MOSAiC freeze-
 440 up period, including average estimated thickness (a) and absolute salinity (b) of meltwater layers in leads (purple),
 441 and melt ponds (blue). Meltwater layer thickness is defined here as the depth of maximum change in density.

442 Markers indicate different measurement platforms, where circles indicate YSI probe (Smith et al., 2021), triangles
 443 are fishing-rod CTD, squares mass-balance transects (Webster et al., 2022), and x's are RINKO CTD. Vertical grey
 444 dashed lines correspond to dates of profiles in **Figure 8**. Blue vertical line indicates first date of surface freezing on
 445 leads and ponds.

446

447 **Figure 7. Exemplary lead meltwater layer profiles from the MOSAiC expedition during melt season, July 2020.**
 448 Example lead profiles from July 9, 17, and 24 of (a) temperature and (b) absolute salinity, measured by YSI probe.
 449 Dates correspond to vertical grey dashed lines in **Figure 5**

450

Exemplary lead meltwater layer profiles, August-September

451 **Figure 8. Exemplary lead meltwater layer profiles from the MOSAiC expedition during freeze-up, August-**
452 **September 2020. Example lead profiles from August 24, September 5, and September 9 of (a) temperature and (b)**
453 **absolute salinity, measured using fishing-rod CTD. Dates correspond to vertical grey dashed lines in Figure 6.**
454

455
456 In future work, additional MOSAiC datasets will be compiled to estimate a complete budget of
457 freshwater sources and sinks from melt into freeze-up. Quantifying the relative contribution of
458 direct precipitation, snow melt, and sea ice melt to freshwater reservoirs and their fate on the ice,
459 in meltwater layers, or in the ocean below will improve predictions of how these features vary
460 spatially and are likely to evolve in the future.
461

462 6. Implications for the sea ice

463 The presence of a relatively fresh meltwater layer directly below the sea ice impacts how the sea
464 ice evolves over the course of the melt season and how it interacts with the ocean below.
465 Notably, the meltwater layer impacts the sea ice volume with implications for larger scale ice
466 mass balance. The presence of the meltwater layer can slow bottom ablation (Smith, 2019), and
467 even contribute to growth of additional ice as false bottoms through diffusion at the stratified
468 interface. The contribution of the meltwater layer to false bottom formation is perhaps the best
469 documented impact of meltwater layers in prior literature. Thickness estimates for false bottoms
470 typically range from 0.02 m when initially growing to 0.2 m when fully developed (Untersteiner
471 and Badgley, 1958; Hanson, 1965; Eicken, 1994). In various sectors of the Arctic, they have
472 been observed from 10-20% (Eicken, 1994; Perovich et al., 2003) of observation locations. In
473 dedicated sampling of false bottom occurrence during the MOSAiC expedition, they were
474 observed with about 20% frequency with average thickness of 0.08 m (Smith et al., 2022). The
475 temporal evolution of false bottom thickness observed from multiple sites is summarized in
476 **Figure 9**, with photos from selected days showing the physical structure and appearance from
477 below. False bottom thickness increased over the first half of July, to a maximum thickness of
478 just over 0.1 m on average, then subsequently thinned and disappeared as mixing increased and
479 warmer, saltier water reached the false bottom (Salganik et al., 2022; Smith et al., 2022).
480

481
 482 **Figure 9. False bottom thickness evolution during MOSAiC.** Summary of temporal evolution of false bottom
 483 thickness, combining data from Smith et al. (2022b) and Salganik et al. (2022). Observations are compared with
 484 model results from Alexandrov & Nizovtseva (2008) using a drag coefficient of 6×10^{-4} and forced with SIMBA
 485 observations (Salganik et al., 2022). Bottom left: Photo of false bottom collected at the MOSAiC first-year ice (FYI)
 486 coring site on July 13, 2020, with an approximate thickness of 0.09 m. The band of darker ice midway through the
 487 ice is likely indicative of a biota layer (Photo credit: Allison Fong). Right: Photo still from GoPro video of false
 488 bottom observed from below near the FYI coring site IMB buoy on July 25, 2020. Videos available in Smith et al.
 489 (2022b).

490 Process models have provided insights on the expected evolution and impact of false bottoms
 491 (Notz et al., 2003; Alexandrov & Nizovtseva, 2008; Smith, 2019). Notz et al. (2003) presented
 492 an analytical model describing the formation by diffusion of heat and salt, which was able to
 493 capture features of observed evolution in the Arctic. False bottom processes were similarly
 494 modeled in one-dimension by Alexandrov & Nizovtseva (2008) (**Figure 9**). Modeling by Smith
 495 (2019) incorporated the sea ice slab above and horizontal aspects of growth. This latter model
 496 suggested significant local impacts on sea ice mass balance, where ice with false bottoms would
 497 be 1-8% thicker than ice without. Application of the Notz et al. (2003) false bottom model to
 498 MOSAiC observations was able to capture aspects of growth but not all of the subsequent melt
 499 (Smith et al., 2022a; Salganik et al., 2022), while the model from Alexandrov & Nizovtseva
 500 (2008) shows good comparison with MOSAiC coring site observations in **Figure 9**. Although
 501 this work and other evidence (e.g., Eicken, 1994) suggests the impact of widespread false
 502 bottoms on regional sea ice mass balance, parameterizations have not yet been developed for the
 503 basin scale. In the absence of a sufficient parameterization for large-scale application, Tsamados
 504 et al. (2015) used a simple adjustment to the heat transfer coefficient based on surface melt pond
 505 concentration to account for the formation of false bottoms. However, there is a lack of data
 506 quantifying the relationship of false bottoms with surface melt ponds and their contribution to the
 507 overall mass balance. Refinement of our understanding of the controls on meltwater layer

508 evolution is needed to improve modeling of false bottoms such that it can be applied in the future
509 on the large scale.

510
511 Over the same time period as false bottom formation on the MOSAiC expedition, it was
512 observed that the conductive heat transfer associated with false bottom presence opposed the
513 ocean heat flux and subsequently slowed sea ice bottom melt (Salganik et al., in review). In
514 neighboring areas that started with the same average ice thickness, ice with false bottoms was 7-
515 8% thicker than ice without false bottoms, in line with the range from prior model estimates
516 (Smith, 2019). Conversely, it has also been proposed that the stratified meltwater layer can
517 accumulate heat (Langleben, 1996; Granskog et al., 2015), which could alternatively lead to an
518 increase in bottom ablation. Whether this meltwater layer ultimately increases or decreases
519 bottom ablation of the overlying ice is a function of whether the driving factor in basal melt is
520 local solar warming, which can lead to increased melt, or heat in the mixed layer, which can
521 become isolated from the ice bottom. While observations during MOSAiC suggest that the latter
522 dominates, this may vary under different conditions, such as below thin ice. Meltwater
523 infiltration additionally has an important and concentrated impact in the mass balance of ridges,
524 where re-freezing of the relatively fresh meltwater can result in rapid ridge keel consolidation in
525 the melting season (Marchenko, 2022; Lange et al. in review). This effectively increases the sea
526 ice volume and slows subsequent ridge keel melt.

527
528 The infiltration of this relatively fresh layer can lead to physical changes in the sea ice above
529 through desalinization. During the melt season, sea ice with underlying meltwater layers often
530 exhibits reduced salinity near the bottom. Eicken (1994) observed differences in bottom salinity
531 of level ice with and without an underlying meltwater layer of 0.4-0.7 ppt vs. 3.1 ppt,
532 respectively, indicating desalination by meltwater flushing. Polashenski et al. (2015) observed
533 low $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and salinities at the top and bottom of ice cores in the Beaufort Sea, indicative of the
534 infiltration and re-freezing of meltwater. During MOSAiC, FYI in the presence of an under-ice
535 meltwater layer decreased in bulk salinity from 4.4–5.3 g/kg in winter and spring to 1.1 g/kg by
536 the end of July (Salganik et al., in review), which is half of that commonly observed for Arctic
537 FYI with similar thickness during the melt season (Wang et al., 2020).

538
539 The presence of meltwater layers in leads during the summer typically results in enhanced lateral
540 melting of sea ice, as was previously observed during the SHEBA expedition (Richter-Menge et
541 al., 2001) and an experiment in Mould Bay (Perovich and Maykut, 1990). The strong
542 stratification of thin, meltwater layers allows solar heat to build up primarily in these layers,
543 while present. Perovich and Maykut (1990) noted that increased turbidity in lead meltwater
544 layers, presumably associated with an algal bloom, led to nearly complete absorption of solar
545 energy in this layer. During their study, similar structure was not observed in more mobile ice at
546 a nearby site, indicating the importance of quiescence in forming meltwater layers and
547 subsequent accumulation of heat. When wind or ice drift causes mixing through the meltwater
548 layer, its heat can then be rapidly released, resulting in large increases in both lateral and bottom
549 melt. In Mould Bay, heat buildup in the layer itself was minimal as there was sufficient mixing
550 from wind that it led directly to lateral melting, with a total of 1.5 m lateral melt over the course
551 of the experiment surrounding the initially 3 m-wide lead (Perovich and Maykut, 1990). Due to
552 the role that lateral melting plays in forming open water and decreasing local albedo, the basin-
553 wide sea ice pack is quite sensitive to the temperature difference in leads driving this melt (e.g.,

554 Smith et al. 2022c). The lateral melt rate abutting leads with thin, meltwater layers with evolving
555 heat content on MOSAiC will be targeted in future studies in order to understand the role of
556 atmospheric and oceanic factors on the resulting melt.

557
558 Following the summer season, the persistence of fresher meltwater in melt ponds and in the
559 upper ocean into fall and winter can have impacts on sea ice freeze-up and subsequent evolution.
560 During fall at MOSAiC, meltwater freshening of the upper ocean resulted in increased freezing
561 temperature, which terminated basal melting and pre-conditioned freeze-up (Kawaguchi et al.,
562 2022). Meltwater layers in leads similarly may result in earlier freezing at these locations
563 because fresher water freezes at a higher temperature than more saline water (Nomura et al. in
564 review). Refrozen leads and melt ponds from the preceding summer are visible in winter as
565 warm surface temperature anomalies (Thielke et al., 2022), which may suggest an extended
566 impact on the annual cycle depending on the growth history.

567 7. Implications for the ocean

568
569 The large salinity difference between the meltwater layers and the underlying ocean water results
570 in stratification approximately two orders of magnitude stronger than in the halocline underlying
571 the mixed layer (**Figure 10**; Golovin & Ivanov, 2015; Perovich et al., 2021; Richter-Menge et
572 al., 2001). However, spatial variability in ice conditions, melt rates, and turbulent mixing can set
573 up substantial lateral gradients on scales on the order of 1 km (Timmermans and Winsor, 2013).
574 The meltwater does not necessarily remain stationary, and so it sometimes is hard to distinguish
575 between a newly formed meltwater layer and an already relatively fresh surface mixed layer. For
576 example, observations from the Pacific sector of the Arctic have shown that the evolution of
577 meltwater layers might be impacted by advection and horizontal stirring (Peralta-Ferriz &
578 Woodgate, 2015). In the Atlantic sector of the Amundsen and Makarov Basins, observations
579 have shown meltwater layers embedded within relatively low salinity upper ocean layers
580 (Rudels, 2016). Both the size of ice floes and the presence of ocean eddies likely play a role in
581 the lateral redistribution of meltwater (Horvat et al., 2016). We can additionally expect that
582 meltwater layers will reduce mixed layer instabilities by reducing mixed layer depth H and
583 increasing stratification N , as they occur on their Rossby deformation radius, NH/f , where f is the
584 Coriolis parameter.
585

586 **Figure 10. Buoyancy frequency N^2 of the near-surface ocean before and after a storm.** Profiles from before the
 587 storm observed during MOSAiC expedition Leg 5 (24 August – 6 September; blue) show a meltwater layer in the
 588 upper meter, which is absent following mixing from storm (7 September – 9 September; red). The stratification of
 589 the meltwater layer in (a) is approximately 2 orders-of-magnitude stronger than the mixed layer halocline in (b).
 590 Thick lines show the mean profile over the given time period, and thin lines show individual profiles. The profiles
 591 were collected using a hand-held fishing-rod CTD from the ice.
 592

593
 594 Situated directly at the interface between atmosphere, sea ice, and the underlying ocean, the
 595 presence of these meltwater layers influences the vertical transfer of momentum, heat, and salt
 596 (Vihma et al., 2014).
 597 A meltwater layer stabilizes the ocean boundary layer under ice (the upper few meters), increases
 598 the potential energy, and thereby requires more energy from turbulence to move fresh water
 599 downward against the buoyancy force. The maximum turbulence mixing scale is reduced, with
 600 impacts on the ice-ocean drag (Kudryavtsev and Soloviev, 1990; McPhee et al., 1987). The
 601 frictional coupling between the ice and ocean, hence drag, is reduced, making the mixed layer
 602 more “slippery”. Furthermore, the turning angle of the Ekman layer will increase. During the N-
 603 ICE2015 campaign north of Svalbard, meltwater in the upper ocean was observed to reduce the
 604 upper ocean turbulent mixing (Randelhoff et al., 2017). While the meltwater layers they
 605 observed were an order-of-magnitude greater in thickness and salinity than those we are
 606 primarily interested in here, the physical process likely extends to the smaller scale and higher
 607 stratification scenario.
 608

609 Similar to sea ice (Martin et al., 2014), the meltwater layer can act as a lid on the ocean, reducing
 610 the transfer of momentum from the atmosphere. Specifically, the turbulent ocean boundary layer
 611 acts as a sink for wind energy, such that the fraction of energy redistributed to the deeper layers
 612 in the water column is reduced. As a result, meltwater layers may alter the near-inertial energy
 613 propagating downwards in the Arctic Ocean (Morison et al., 1985). They can also interact with
 614 sea ice to generate ice-ocean drag in these layers mediated by internal waves (McPhee and

615 Kantha, 1989). During the MOSAiC expedition, an upward-rising VMP was used to understand
 616 near-surface turbulence and the effect of melting on the turbulent boundary layer (Fer et al.,
 617 2022a; 2022b). The disruption of the under-ice meltwater layer in mid-late July (see Section 5)
 618 has implications for the upper ocean structure and turbulent transport. The effect of this
 619 evolution on the momentum transfer between the surface and the mixed layer is still an open
 620 question that should be the target of future observations and studies.
 621
 622

623 **Figure 11. Profiles from the VMP contrast the upper 3 m in the presence and absence of a meltwater layer.** All
 624 profiles were collected in leads. A) Temperature, b) approximate practical salinity (see Supplementary material Text
 625 S1), and c) the dissipation rate, (ϵ). In the profiles collected on 17 July and in the afternoon of 21 July (thick lines)
 626 the profiler surfaced under pack ice or close to the ice edge where no meltwater layer was detected. Legend
 627 indicates the day, approximate start and end hour of the day, and the number of profiles averaged.
 628

629 Several profiles from the ascending VMP showed indications of a thin meltwater layer (Figure
 630 11; thin lines). Contrasting average dissipation profiles in the presence and absence of a
 631 meltwater layer suggests the turbulence is suppressed by 1-2 orders of magnitude in the upper
 632 meters of the water column. This is not limited to the meltwater layer (<1m), but extends
 633 downward at least 3 m. Of course, this only illustrates the effect of a meltwater layer on a
 634 relatively non-turbulent environment – high turbulence, for example during strong wind events,
 635 may in turn mix and erode away the meltwater layer, as observed during MOSAiC (e.g. Figure
 636 7). The methods used to produce these figures are described in Supplementary material Text S1;
 637 a more detailed analysis is not justified given that the profiles have large uncertainties and did
 638 not target the meltwater layer specifically.
 639

640 Meltwater retention near the surface also affects the salt and heat balance of the mixed layer
 641 below (Kadko et al. 2000). As the late summer solar heating is primarily absorbed in the
 642 meltwater layers (Granskog et al., 2015), the presence of meltwater layers can limit the solar
 643 warming of the underlying mixed layer. At the same time, it results in a faster temperature

644 increase at the surface since less heat is distributed into the underlying mixed layer (Rudels, 2012
645 & 2016). In this manner, the presence of meltwater layers impacts the partitioning of solar heat
646 between ice melt and warming of the water column resulting in more heat being retained in the
647 ocean (e.g., Hudson et al. 2013), Granskog et al. (2015). Idealized simulations performed by
648 Skyllingstad et al. (2005) and observations from Randelhoff et al. (2014) show that the presence
649 of a meltwater layer also impedes downward mixing of solar heat and upward mixing of colder
650 or warmer water. At the same time, increased turbidity in meltwater layers, such as from algal
651 blooms, increases the absorption and solar heating of the upper few meters (Perovich & Maykut
652 1990; Pegau et al., 2002; Taskjelle et al., 2017). Observations have shown notable heat
653 accumulated in meltwater layers in leads (Richter-Menge et al., 2001; Perovich and Maykut,
654 1990). Similarly, Langleben (1966) documented an increase in the temperature of under-ice
655 meltwater layers associated with solar input by approximately 1°C over the melt season, which
656 resulted in rapid bottom melt towards the end of the observations. Meltwater layers can thus both
657 increase and decrease bottom melt depending on if the dominant heat source is the solar heating
658 from above or warmer ocean waters below. Solar heating also results in a small increase in the
659 stability of the stratification; however, the thermal contribution to the stratification is small
660 compared to the haline contribution, especially at low temperatures (Sigman et al., 2004).

661
662 Meltwater layers have a notable impact on upper ocean optics under and surrounding sea ice.
663 Largely, the optical impacts are associated with increased concentration of scattering particles,
664 such as algae (see Sect. 8) in the meltwater layer or at the lower interface. Previous observations
665 show a peak in absorption spectra and increased scattering in under-ice meltwater layers
666 associated with algae aggregates, with implications for the under-ice light environment (Ehn et
667 al., 2011, Bélanger et al., 2013). Granskog et al. (2015) observed that sea ice meltwater can also
668 act as a source introducing scattering particles to the under-ice layer of the upper ocean that are
669 not related to under-ice blooms. Ultimately, scattering particles of either biogenic or other
670 sources will increase scattering and reduce transmission of light and solar energy to the ocean
671 below. We also note that the presence of such layers may impact satellite retrievals of
672 chlorophyll and other relevant variables through the influence on upper ocean optics and light
673 attenuation.

674

675 **Figure 12.** Schematic overview of key ecological, biogeochemical, and atmospheric processes discussed in
676 Sections 8-10, including meltwater in melt ponds, leads, and under the sea ice. Figure by Madison Smith & Natalie
677 Renier © Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
678

679 8. Organism diversity and community structure within and below the meltwater 680 layer

681 Melt ponds and meltwater layers in leads and underneath sea ice create ephemeral ecological
682 habitats with microbial communities that are distinct from sea ice and bulk seawater. Distinct
683 niches are expected to develop as the melting season progresses, causing shifts in community
684 composition with cascading impacts on ecosystem functionality, productivity, and food quality
685 for higher trophic levels. Past work on microbial communities of brackish and freshwater
686 habitats in the Arctic Ocean has provided insights into how habitat transitions shape the diversity
687 and activity of these communities (Brinkmeyer et al. 2004; Fernández-Méndez et al. 2016; Xu et
688 al. 2020; Hancke et al. 2022). However, detailed data on the evolution of these habitats, along
689 with information on the seasonal cycle of sea ice and seawater properties, are required to
690 understand how they recruit their microbiomes and how dispersal contributes to the development
691 of these ephemeral ecosystems.

692 Melting sea ice and snow significantly shape the microbial assemblages in meltwater habitats, in
693 part through stress responses to their shifting environmental conditions (Hatam et al. 2016; Rapp
694 et al. 2021; Figure 11). Microbes inhabiting sea ice are highly adapted to harsh hypersaline
695 conditions in sea ice brine pockets (Rapp et al. 2021; Mock et al. 2017; Junge et al. 2004). The
696 transition into a hyposaline environment upon melt, or meltwater flushing of basal sea ice
697 (Salganik et al., in review, see section 6) causes osmotic, ionic, and oxidative stress, resulting in
698 cell loss and impairing various cellular functions, such as photosynthetic activity or membrane
699 integrity, and ultimately growth rates (Kirst 1989, Arrigo & Sullivan, 1992, Ralph et al. 2007b,
700 Antoni et al. 2020, Chamberlain et al. 2022). Additional stressors in under-ice meltwater, such as
701 high irradiances and low macronutrient concentrations, can augment stress. For example,
702 hyposalinity and nutrient limitation increase susceptibility of microalgae to high light stress,
703 enhancing the potential for photodamage, oxidative stress (Ralph et al. 2005, Petrou et al. 2011),
704 and decreasing capacity for biomass production (Behrenfeld et al. 2008). In prokaryotic
705 (bacterial and archaeal) communities, fluctuations in salinity conditions are more stressful than
706 temperature extremes, with survival largely dependent on the availability of solutes for
707 osmoprotection (Ewert and Deming 2014).

708 Certain species can acclimatize to these new environmental conditions on a timescale of days to
709 weeks (Grant & Horner 1976), by changing fatty acid composition, concentrations of
710 osmoregulatory compounds, or light-harvesting characteristics of the photosynthetic apparatus
711 (Kirst 1989, Hernando et al. 2018, Bowman et al. 2021). Autotrophic flagellates generally seem
712 to be better able to acclimate to meltwater habitats than diatoms, often dominating algal
713 communities in persistent low-salinity meltwater layers and potentially initiating meltwater
714 under-ice blooms (Gradinger, 1996; Mundy et al., 2011). However, a spectrum exists also within
715 the group of diatoms, where some species, e.g. *Fragilariopsis*, *Chaetoceros*, *Attheya*, are more
716 resilient to low salinity than others, e.g. *Nitzschia*, *Cylindrotheca* (Allen 1971, Zhang et al. 1999,
717 Hernando et al. 2015, Ryan et al. 2004, Antoni et al. 2020). At the interface between meltwater
718 and seawater, another unique algae community, originally termed ‘halocline flora’, can establish

719 (Apollonio, 1980; Apollonio, 1985; Apollonio and Matrai, 2011; McLaren, 1969). The halocline
 720 community typically occurs within the upper 2 m of the water column, can last for up to 8 weeks
 721 with constant high biomass levels of 1 to 2 mg Chl *a* m⁻³, and has been observed to be dominated
 722 by phototrophic flagellates Chlorophyceae and Chrysophyceae (Bursa, 1963). Distinctive
 723 bacterial communities have also been observed between the surface and subsurface of meltwater
 724 rich environments (Zeng et al. 2013).

725

726
 727 **Figure 13. Example microbial community structure and ecophysiology from a stratified lead meltwater layer**
 728 **from the MOSAiC Drift in July.** A) Image on the left shows a relatively thin ca. 1-2 cm, high biomass layer located

729 at the interface between meltwater and seawater observed on July 7th (Muilwijk et al., 2022). Temperature (° C)
730 and salinity values for these targeted layers were measured using a YSI probe prior to water sampling on July 10th
731 (see section 5; Smith et al., 2022b). Targeted sampling of this layer took place on July 10th and 11th, with the
732 images on the right showcasing differences in water pigmentation from each layer (bottles from left to right:
733 meltwater, interface, underlying seawater and filtered biomass from left to right: meltwater, interface). B) The
734 relative abundance of prokaryotic bacteria and archaea community members, as well as the total cell abundances of
735 bacteria, High Nucleic Acid (HNA) containing bacteria, Low Nucleic Acid (LNA) containing bacteria, and viral
736 particles in the meltwater layer, interface, and underlying seawater. C) The relative abundance of eukaryotic
737 community members as well as total cell abundances of picophytoplankton and nanophytoplankton, chlorophyll
738 concentration, and effective quantum yield in the meltwater layer, interface, and underlying seawater. Data
739 information and methods used are available in supplemental material.

740 During July-September of the MOSAiC Expedition (both drift tracks; **Figure 2**), the distribution
741 of algae was visibly stratified across salinity gradients in the upper 2 m of the surface ocean,
742 often with community assemblages in the under-ice or lead meltwater layer that were distinct
743 from the underlying seawater. In early July, a halocline high biomass layer was observed
744 accumulating at the interface between the meltwater layer and underlying seawater, when the
745 meltwater layer thickness was still increasing (**Figure 5**). This visibly dense biomass layer was
746 estimated to be approximately 1-2 cm thick, based on video images and sampling attempts
747 (**Figure 13A**), with a protist community primarily composed of previously described halocline
748 biota pico-eukaryotes such as pelagophytes and dinoflagellates
749 (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/895866>). For example, on July 11th, this biomass-
750 dense interface was high in Chl *a*, with an autotrophic community structure more similar
751 (qualitatively) to the underlying seawater than the overlying meltwater layer (**Figure 13C**). Both
752 hetero- and autotrophic microorganisms were more abundant below the halocline, and lowest
753 abundances were measured in the meltwater layer. This indicates that biomass in the meltwater
754 layer was low. Additionally, particles with high Chl *a* content (4.7 µg L⁻¹) along the interface
755 were likely larger than 10-15 µm, which is roughly the size limit for flow cytometry. The
756 bacterial cells present in the meltwater layer had higher proportions of Gammaproteobacteria and
757 Flavobacteria than the underlying seawater. These taxa are commonly enriched in sea ice and
758 may have originated from that environment (Bowman, 2015). The melt layer also had a large
759 proportion of Actinomycetia, or Actinobacteria, common to Arctic permafrost environments
760 (Boetius et al. 2015), which may have originated from snow or sediment entrained in the
761 MOSAiC ice floe (Krumpfen et al. 2020). The eukaryotic community present in the meltwater
762 layer was similarly indicative of an ice-based community and enriched in taxa common in sea
763 ice.

764 Studies using high-throughput sequencing of phylogenetic marker and functional genes show
765 that microbial communities of relatively fresh layers are largely distinct from sea ice and
766 adjacent sea water only if exchange is limited (Xu et al. 2020). For instance, melt ponds that are
767 enclosed appear to be dominated by β-proteobacteria (Brinkmeyer et al. 2004) and more
768 mixotrophic and heterotrophic microbial eukaryotes (Xu et al. 2020). However, as soon as
769 meltwater habitats in leads and under-ice meltwater ponds are in closer exchange with nutrient-
770 richer seawater, different microbial communities seem to thrive (Hancke et al. 2022). These
771 communities often appear to be dominated by photosynthetic microbes, including the keystone
772 diatom *Melosira arctica* (Hancke et al. 2022), which was observed in high biomass for ice-
773 associated communities from July to September during MOSAiC.

774

775

776 **Figure 14. *Melosira arctica* progression and meltwater layer evolution.** A) Three images taken
 777 at the same spot, facing the same direction underneath a bore hole through first year sea ice.
 778 From left to right: 28.06.2020; 05.07.2020; 19.07.2020. The second image also shows platelet
 779 ice. B) Image from beneath a lead surface with meltwater layer from 22.07.2020 taken from
 780 video footage. C) Image from beneath a lead surface during the northern positioning of the Leg
 781 5 drift track, with visible suspended algal aggregates taken from video footage. Original videos
 782 from which stills B) and C) were taken are available in the supplemental material.

783 *Melosira arctica* is a sympagic diatom that forms up to meter-long filaments. Cryoprotective and
 784 adhesive properties provided by extracellular mucus consisting of polymeric substances allow
 785 them to attach to the under-ice surface (Krembs et al., 2002; Abdullahi et al., 2006; Aslam et al.,
 786 2012). As the meltwater layer developed underneath the ice during July of MOSAiC, *Melosira*
 787 *arctica* strands were observed to detach from the under-ice surface (**Figure 14A**), followed by
 788 disintegration of the long filaments into smaller aggregates, many of which were bleached in
 789 appearance (**Figure 14B**). Previous studies have shown that sub-ice algal aggregates can
 790 account for up to 94 % of local primary production (Fernández-Méndez et al. 2014) and
 791 associate the release of *Melosira arctica* from the sea ice with sea ice melt and subsequent
 792 sedimentation (Boetius et al., 2013; Michel et al., 1997; Riesebell et al., 1991; Bauerfeind et al.,
 793 1997; Tremblay et al., 1989), making it an important factor in the high Arctic biological carbon
 794 pump. The buoyancy of aggregates may be regulated by oxygen bubbles within the mucus that
 795 are formed during photosynthesis under favorable light conditions (Fernandéz-Méndez et al.,
 796 2014). A working hypothesis is that the accumulation of cells at the meltwater-seawater interface
 797 is driven by 1) buoyancy of cells living underneath the meltwater layer that rise to the surface
 798 where light and nutrient availability allow these and other photoautotrophs to thrive (Hancke et
 799 al., 2022), and 2) by the strong density gradient of the meltwater gradient acting as a barrier for
 800 continued upward (pelagic community) or downward (ice-associated community) movement of
 801 cells. In meltwater layers observed later in the season and further north (August-September),
 802 biomass was no longer visibly enhanced at the meltwater halocline but suspended within the
 803 meltwater layer, with algal aggregates and bleached particulate organic matter potentially fueling
 804 secondary production and regeneration processes within the meltwater layer (Figure 13C).
 805 Similar drifting aggregates observed on other expeditions were dominated by pennate sea-ice
 806 diatoms within a mucous matrix and can support high levels of local biological activity and
 807 zooplankton grazing (Assmy et al., 2013).

808 Indeed, the abundance of photoautotrophs in under-ice water creates an important feeding- and
809 nursery ground for zooplankton. They include sympagic sub-ice fauna that migrate here from the
810 ice interior and pelagic sub-ice fauna that arrive from the water column. The sympagic fauna –
811 e.g., copepods *Halectinosoma spp.*, *Tisbe spp.* and ice amphipods *Apherusa glacialis* and
812 *Onisimus glacialis* – dominate the under-ice habitat during early summer when a pronounced
813 layer of meltwater is present (Werner, 2006) and are derived from meltwater flushing, expelling
814 ice fauna from their brine channel habitat. Their large osmotic tolerance enables them to survive
815 in the brackish meltwater (Aarset and Aunaas, 1990, Werner, 2006). In contrast, pelagic
816 copepods (e.g., *Pseudocalanus spp.*, *Oithona similis*, *Oncaea borealis* and *Calanus hyperboreus*)
817 are more sensitive to low salinities (Grainger and Mohammed, 1990, Weslawski and
818 Legezynska, 1998) and accumulate at the periphery of the meltwater layer, where they benefit
819 from aggregated food (Hop et al., 2011). Indeed, meltwater layers can sometimes prove
820 detrimental to sampling efforts of these more sensitive communities for experimental work.
821 During July of the MOSAiC Expedition, a vertical zooplankton net tow underneath the ice
822 (conducted 3 days after the meltwater layer was observed in a nearby lead) and subsequent
823 rinsing of the net with surface water resulted in the death of all animals collected, most likely due
824 to osmotic stress from meltwater (Gelfman, personal communication, 2022). With the
825 progressive loss of sea ice over the summer, the sympagic fauna at the surface is gradually
826 replaced by pelagic zooplankton. In previous studies, dense concentrations or ‘swarms’ of the
827 copepod *Calanus glacialis* were associated with the meltwater layer, and their green guts
828 indicated the use of the rich food supply before overwintering (Werner, 2006, Hop et al., 2011).
829 These swarms provide a potential food source to higher trophic levels. For example, cold-
830 adapted fish, like polar cod, have been observed to congregate or take refuge in meltwater layers
831 and associated habitats, such as the void space between false bottoms and pack ice (**Figure 15**).

832

833

834 **Figure 15.** Fish (likely polar cod) using the void space between false bottom and pack ice as refuge during a
835 research cruise on *RV Polarstern (PS131)* during summer 2022. Also visible are brown and bleached algal
836 biomass aggregates.

837 The vertically condensed structure of lead meltwater also provides a unique habitat for
838 examining intensive microbial loop processes that are involved in the decomposition of organic
839 matter and regeneration of nutrients. One hypothesis that future work will test is that the
840 meltwater and interface layers could harbor separate microbial loop systems, with potentially
841 different consequences for cycling of nutrients, organic matter (OM), and the structuring of

842 microbial assemblages as these layers change under future ice conditions (Lannuzel et al., 2020).
843 Hypothetically, the microbial loop system within the meltwater layer could be dominated by
844 recycling of sea ice OM, which was incorporated into the ice column during ice growth and
845 released during the onset of melting. In some instances, the ratios of particulate organic carbon to
846 nitrogen POC:PON of sea ice OM could reflect higher proportions of refractory material relative
847 to freshly generated OM during the growth season (Juhl et al. 2011; Jørgensen et al. 2015;
848 Underwood et al. 2019). Proportions of refractory to labile OM in the meltwater layer - currently
849 unknown - could influence the composition of microbial assemblages and rates of
850 remineralization activity. Different nutrients, organic or inorganic, play a vital role in driving
851 different microbial activities across the meltwater system. Genetic information on marine
852 microbial assemblages provide insights into the capacity of microbes to utilize organic forms of
853 dissolved nitrogen and phosphorus (Grossart et al., 2020), and under which conditions these
854 capacities would be advantageous. For instance, Chrysophyceae and ciliates tend to dominate the
855 mixotrophic and heterotrophic microbial eukaryotes found in freshwater layers (Xu et al. 2020),
856 which suggests that nutrient sources within this habitat are mainly based on consumption of
857 recycled organic material rather than mixing or upwelling. This is corroborated by studies that
858 found low concentrations of essential inorganic nutrients e.g. phosphate, nitrate in freshwater
859 melt ponds (Sørensen et al. 2017).

860 Despite these exciting insights from previous studies, many questions surrounding the ecology of
861 these ephemeral yet persistent meltwater habitats remain to be quantified and addressed. Key
862 questions for future work include identifying the exact sources of microbes that thrive and/or
863 accumulate in ephemeral meltwater habitats and the physiological adaptations that allow them to
864 do so. The level of endemism and presence of novel species in freshwater microbial communities
865 need to be identified to understand the overall contribution of ephemeral meltwater habitats to
866 the biodiversity of the Arctic Ocean and how it might change in a warming Arctic. Using the
867 wealth of genetic data collected during the MOSAiC Expedition (Mock et al. 2022), many of
868 these questions will be explored in future studies. Additionally, the strategic interdisciplinary
869 sampling scheme employed on MOSAiC for these environments (see section 4) will allow
870 further exploration of key biological drivers of meltwater biogeochemical cycling, such as
871 identifying the impact of meltwater microbial communities on sea ice-seawater gas, nutrient, and
872 particle exchange and quantifying the contributions of meltwater microbes to air-sea gas
873 exchange. Future work using data from targeted sampling of the different meltwater habitats
874 during the melt and freeze-up periods of MOSAiC, in collaboration with co-sampling of
875 biogeochemical variables and flux measurements, will expand insights to new horizons.
876

877 9. Biogeochemical gradients across the meltwater/seawater interface and 878 implications for air–sea exchange of gases and aerosols

879 In general, biogenic gases (e.g., dissolved oxygen (DO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄),
880 nitrous oxide (N₂O), dimethylsulfoniopropionate (DMSP), and dimethylsulfide (DMS)) and
881 aerosols are produced, consumed, or cycled by the microbial community in surface waters. They
882 can be emitted to the atmosphere, where they subsequently have significant effects on climate
883 and support further biological processes. Although recent observations indicate that some gas
884 exchange does occur through sea ice (e.g., Delille et al., 2014), sea ice generally acts as a
885 physical barrier for direct sea–air flux. Thus, summer sea ice melt is thought to enhance
886 exchange between the ocean and the atmosphere by increasing open water area (Parmentier et

887 al., 2013). However, the presence of meltwater layers in leads and in melt ponds may limit the
888 exchange of climate-relevant trace gases and aerosols across the air-sea interface.

889 Here, we first summarize what is known about the impact of meltwater layers on the production
890 and turnover of these gases in the upper ocean, with aggregated biological material immediately
891 below the meltwater layer (Nansen, 1902; Perovich & Maykut 1990) and strong stratification
892 expected to impact biogeochemical processes involved in elemental cycling. Given the sparsity
893 of knowledge on biogenic gas concentrations in the Arctic upper ocean, observations during the
894 MOSAiC expedition provide unique insight into concentrations in the near-surface meltwater
895 layers during melt (Figure 15) and freeze-up (Figure 16) periods. We also discuss the overall
896 effect of thin meltwater layers on air-sea exchange of these gases and aerosols.

897
898
899 **Figure 16. Exemplary profiles of biogenic gases from meltwater layers during the MOSAiC expedition melt**
900 **season, July 2020.** Example profiles from July 17th from leads (purple) and under ice water (green), showing
901 discrete samples for a) salinity (measured using YSI (Smith et al., 2022b) and MSS (Schulz et al., 2022)), (b) DMS
902 (solid lines) and DMSP (dashed lines)(analysed using PTR-MS), (c) percentage saturation of dissolved oxygen
903 (calculated from MSS on 7th July) and (d) dissolved methane (analysed by Picarro) on July 11 due to unavailability
904 of data on other dates.

906
907

908 **Figure 17. Exemplary profiles of biogenic gases from meltwater layers during the MOSAiC expedition during**
 909 **freeze-up, August-September 2020. Example profiles from September 2nd from meltponds (teal) and leads (purple)**
 910 **showing discrete samples for (a) salinity (measured using RINKO CTD), (b) DMS (solid lines) and DMS/P (dashed**
 911 **lines)(analysed using PTR-MS), (c) percentage saturation of dissolved oxygen (calculated from RINKO CTD), (d)**
 912 **pCO₂ (calculated from DIC and TA analysis) and (e) N₂O (analysed by GC-ECD).**

913 9.1 Dissolved Oxygen

914

915 Total DO content in the surface mixed layer of the Arctic Ocean generally shows saturated or
 916 supersaturated values. Conventional discrete sampling of DO from shipborne CTD Rosette
 917 samplers, followed by standard Winkler analysis (Langdon, 2010), shows a mean supersaturation
 918 in total DO of $102.6 \pm 3.5\%$ ($n = 520$) north of 85°N in the upper 10 m of the central Arctic
 919 Ocean (GLODAP v2.2022; Lauvset et al., 2022). Biologically mediated DO supersaturation in
 920 the surface ocean reflects the net metabolic balance between photosynthesis and respiration, i.e.,
 921 net community production (NCP). Historic underway measurements of $\Delta\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ from ~ 10 m
 922 depth show a mean biological DO supersaturation ($\Delta\text{O}_2^{\text{bio}}$) of $3.4 \pm 3.0\%$ ($n = 4477$) north of 85
 923 $^\circ\text{N}$, indicating net autotrophic conditions during late summer (Eveleth et al., 2014; Ulfso et al.,
 924 2014; Ouyang et al., 2021). This excess DO is photosynthetically produced or injected by the
 925 exclusion of dissolved gas by growing ice (Timmermans et al., 2010; Top et al., 1985; Sherr and
 926 Sherr, 2003; Codispoti & Richards, 1971, Loose et al., 2009). Trapping of dissolved gases by the
 927 sea ice cover likely increases the residence time of DO in the mixed layer relative to open ocean
 928 conditions (Eveleth et al., 2014), but conversely, sea ice melt is depleted in DO compared to the
 929 ambient seawater and can become a significant sink of DO compared to its sea ice precursor
 930 upon melting (Glud et al., 2002; Rysgaard and Glud, 2004; Rysgaard et al., 2008). Depending on
 931 melt rate and stratification, DO-depleted sea ice meltwater can lead to undersaturated surface
 932 waters, thereby driving a downward flux of oxygen at air-ice-sea interfaces (Rysgaard et al.,
 933 2008, 2011). During the MOSAiC melt period, DO was found to be lower in the surface
 934 meltwater layer compared to the layer immediately below the halocline, presumably linked with
 935 high Chl *a* concentrations identified in the interface layer and subsequent photosynthesis
 936 (Section 8; **Figure 13**), which were disconnected with O₂ entering the water from the
 937 atmosphere. There are significant challenges in disentangling the processes underlying the net

938 DO content in the uppermost Arctic Ocean as biological production or consumption is likely to
939 change with season from primary to secondary production, and may often be masked by a much
940 larger physical-induced flux under conditions of sea ice freezing or melting (Glud et al., 2014;
941 Attard et al., 2018).

942

943 9.2 Carbon dioxide

944

945 The concentration of CO₂ in the Arctic Ocean is of key importance in understanding the role of
946 the Arctic in ongoing rising global temperatures. Its concentration is driven by both abiotic and
947 biotic processes, which are likely to have interacting effects on levels in the presence of thin
948 meltwater layers. CO₂ is dissolved in the surface water and is quickly converted to bicarbonate
949 and carbonate ions, releasing hydrogen ions, the so-called carbonate system. Dissolved inorganic
950 carbon (DIC) concentration represents the sum of the dissolved inorganic carbonate species
951 (including CO₂ and carbonic acid) and total alkalinity (TA) is used to measure the buffering
952 capacity against acidic input such as CO₂ (Zeebe & Wolf-Gladrow, 2001). Meltwater, whether
953 from sea ice and snow or glacial origin, reduces the concentrations of these marine carbonate
954 system components through dilution (Chierici and Fransson, 2009). As a result, the partial
955 pressure of CO₂ (pCO₂) in seawater, which can be calculated from DIC and TA (or can be
956 measured directly), decreases, and the ocean can absorb more CO₂ from the atmosphere.
957 However, pCO₂ is also affected by temperature changes, which needs to be taken into account
958 when investigating the drivers. Chierici et al. (2019) suggested that meltwater from sea ice
959 promotes primary production and ocean CO₂ uptake from the atmosphere in the inflowing water
960 to the Arctic Ocean and north of Svalbard. Geilfus et al. (2015) observed low pCO₂ in melt pond
961 water on first-year sea ice in the Canadian Arctic due to the dilution effect of meltwater.
962 (Geilfus et al., 2015). Nomura et al. (2013) similarly showed that snow meltwater on Arctic and
963 Antarctic sea ice results in a drastic decrease of carbonate species concentration in the sea ice
964 environment, and that sea ice therefore acts as a sink for atmospheric CO₂ during periods of
965 snowmelt and surface flooding. However, this simplistic view of changes by dilution is
966 complicated by biological processes dominated by respiration and decay, which produce CO₂,
967 and photosynthesis, which removes CO₂ (e.g., Fransson et al., 2011). As discussed in Section 8,
968 biomass in the meltwater layer is generally low compared to the interface and underlying
969 seawater. In contrast to such snow and sea ice meltwater, glacial meltwater and riverine-derived
970 freshwater can carry significant volumes of sediment, nutrients, rock flour and remineralised
971 particulate matter (Fransson et al., 2015; Horikawa et al., 2022) that can increase primary
972 production and further reduce CO₂ (St Pierre et al. 2019; Tamura et al, 2022).

973 During the freeze-up phase of the MOSAiC expedition (August-September), both oxygen and
974 pCO₂ showed higher concentrations in the meltwater layer samples compared to the samples
975 from the underlying seawater. Indeed, DO percentage saturation on August 28 was as low as
976 60% below the meltwater, compared to 96% at the surface (**Figure 17**). At the same time,
977 Yoshimura et al. (2023, in review) found that while the pCO₂ in the surface layer of the melt
978 pond (0.1 m) was lower (about 326 µatm) than that in the atmosphere (about 400 µatm), lower
979 pCO₂ was observed below the meltwater layer (about 253 µatm), similar to what was observed
980 in the surface waters in the Nansen Basin (Fransson et al., 2017). While the low DO is a
981 consequence of the enhanced secondary production and regeneration (see Section 8), and limited
982 resupply from the atmosphere, these processes would suggest that pCO₂ should be higher

983 through increased respiration. Such a low pCO₂ value at the halocline could be explained by the
984 mixing process of the carbonate system parameters between sea ice meltwater near the surface
985 and seawater in the bottom of the melt pond due to connection with the ocean below. Given the
986 concentrations of both these gases at the surface and the time of the year, it can be inferred that
987 the meltwater layer is absorbing oxygen and CO₂ from the atmosphere.

988 A common method for estimating air–sea CO₂ flux is based on indirect bulk seawater CO₂
989 fugacity measurements from the ship’s seawater inlet often at a depth of 5–6 m (Pierrot et al.,
990 2009) and 11 m on the R/V Polarstern. However, this method can lead to significant biases in
991 CO₂ flux estimates when shallow stratification in the top 10 m occurs in the Arctic (Miller et al.,
992 2019; Dong et al., 2021) as discussed in Sect. 4.1. Direct measurements of sea–air CO₂ fluxes
993 are, unfortunately, scarce, and recent observations during the MOSAiC expedition (Shupe et al.,
994 2022) are expected to provide important contributions.

995 9.3 Nitrous oxide

996 N₂O is a potent greenhouse gas and the first contributor to stratospheric ozone depletion, with an
997 impact comparable to chlorofluorocarbons (Ravishankara et al. 2009; Crutzen, 1970). In the
998 Arctic Ocean, N₂O production is predominantly natural by the processes of nitrification,
999 denitrification and dissimilatory reduction of nitrate to ammonium, rather than through
1000 anthropogenic production. All three processes are driven by archaea and bacteria that produce
1001 N₂O as an intermediate stage of their metabolism (Goreau et al. 1980; Löscher et al. 2012; Smith
1002 and Zimmerman, 1981). Near-surface water N₂O concentration in the North American Arctic
1003 Ocean was found to be associated with production from continental shelf sediments (Fenwick et
1004 al., 2017; Zhan et al. 2017, 2020, Rees et al. 2022), whereas those in the Greenland Basin and
1005 Fram Strait were found to be undersaturated (Rees et al. 2021). N₂O profiles, for melt ponds and
1006 leads during MOSAiC, mimic pCO₂ profiles during the freeze-up season, with a minimum value
1007 at the bottom of the meltwater layer, and an increase of concentrations toward the surface and
1008 underlying sea water (Figure 16).

1009 Similar salinity, pCO₂ and N₂O concentrations at the bottom of melt ponds and in lead water at 1
1010 m depth suggest connection of the melt pond with sea water. The minimum value of N₂O at the
1011 bottom of the meltwater layer can be related to the melting of N₂O depleted sea ice, while the
1012 increase of N₂O at the surface could be due to atmospheric N₂O uptake. N₂O is undersaturated
1013 along both profiles with regard to the atmosphere, with a minimum saturation at the bottom of
1014 the meltwater layer (81.0% and 76.2% for lead and melt pond, respectively), and a near-
1015 equilibrium saturation for underlying sea water (98.1 %). Surface saturation is of 94.0% and
1016 88.2% for lead and melt pond, respectively.

1017 N₂O surface water samples were collected from 13 different melt ponds during freeze-up. The
1018 N₂O concentration ranged from 6.8 to 17.3 nmol L⁻¹ (**Figure 17**; av. 8.5 ± 2.85 nmol L⁻¹) and
1019 was markedly undersaturated compared to the atmosphere (34.9% to 88.2% with an av. of
1020 44.4%). The concentrations of N₂O in the ice beneath the melt pond were lower than in the melt
1021 pond, ranging from 4.1 to 8.2 nmol L⁻¹ (av. 6.2 ± 1.1 nmol L⁻¹). The higher concentration in melt
1022 pond water compared to the underlying ice suggests that N₂O concentrations may increase
1023 during and following melt as a result of the uptake of atmospheric N₂O. Contrary to the
1024 concentrations of DMS that appear to be related to salinity (see below) and its impact on
1025 microbial processes, we did not observe a clear relationship between salinity and N₂O

1026 concentration in the melt ponds. This might suggest a weak contribution of microbial processes,
1027 with primary control by atmospheric exchange. Concentration of N₂O in the surface lead
1028 meltwater layer was higher than in the melt ponds, ranging from 9.0 to 18.1 nmol L⁻¹ (**Figure 17**;
1029 av. 14.2 ± 3.2 nmol L⁻¹) and therefore was also undersaturated relative to the atmosphere (51.6%
1030 to 97.0% with an av. 79.7% ± 16.2%).

1031 9.4 Methane

1032 CH₄ emissions account for 16–25% of atmospheric warming to date (Etminan et al., 2016).
1033 Atmospheric concentrations have nearly tripled since pre-industrial times, with current increases
1034 of 7.3 ± 0.6 ppb yr⁻¹ over 2007-2019 (Dlugokencky, 2021; Schaefer et al., 2016). In the Arctic,
1035 atmospheric CH₄ concentrations are 8–10% higher than the global average, with 1890 ppb on
1036 average (Saunois et al., 2020; Oh et al., 2020); yet very little is known about sea ice effects on
1037 oceanic CH₄ cycling, let alone the impact of thin meltwater layers. Oceanic sources of CH₄ likely
1038 include (a) production from marine bare and vegetated sediments or thawing sub-sea permafrost;
1039 (b) in-situ production in the water column, especially in the coastal ocean because of submarine
1040 groundwater discharge (USEPA, 2010); (c) leaks from geological marine seepage; and (d)
1041 emission from the destabilization of marine hydrates (Saunois et al., 2020). Geological sources
1042 are predominant in the Arctic Ocean, and trigger high dissolved concentrations through the water
1043 column (e.g., Ferré et al., 2020). Nevertheless, recent studies showed a negligible gas exchange
1044 at the air-sea interface from sub-marine emissions (e.g., Fisher et al., 2011). This phenomenon is
1045 likely driven by CH₄ oxidizers, able to metabolize CH₄ as their source of carbon. This group of
1046 organisms, together with methanogens, are responsible for the CH₄ cycle, whose balance
1047 regulates the net CH₄ emissions (Bridgman et al., 2013). Compared to the rest of the globe, the
1048 CH₄ cycle is more dynamic in the Arctic, reflecting intermittent sedimentary sources, sea ice
1049 cover, and dynamic circulation patterns. The sea ice acting as a barrier to gas exchange, sustains
1050 strong disequilibria in gas concentrations between the atmosphere and ice-covered waters
1051 (Silyakova et al., 2022; Denfeld et al., 2018; Butterworth and Miller, 2016; Karlsson et al., 2013;
1052 Loose and Schlosser, 2011; Wand et al., 2006). There is evidence that sea ice affects Arctic
1053 methane cycling, e.g., by acting as a vector for stored methane, transporting it to remote areas far
1054 away from its sources, or diluting its content and inhibiting the exchange between the subsurface
1055 ocean layers and the atmosphere through stronger stratification/isolation (Damm et al., 2018,
1056 Verdugo et al., 2021). Exchange with the atmosphere can take place in open water leads
1057 (Silyakova et al., 2022). Nevertheless, the potential impact of increasing freshwater, either on the
1058 basin scale or from local meltwater, on CH₄ emissions is currently poorly understood (Manning
1059 et al., 2022, 2020; Lamarche-Gagnon et al., 2019).

1060 During MOSAiC, CH₄ was supersaturated in lead meltwater layers relative to the atmospheric
1061 CH₄ capacity (av. 4.19 ± 0.35 nmol L⁻¹), with concentrations higher in the lead meltwater layer
1062 compared to the underlying water (**Figure 16**), suggesting the potential for ventilation into the
1063 atmosphere. (See supplementary material Text S3 for methods). This observation is in contrast to
1064 CO₂ and N₂O observations but in line with earlier studies (Damm et al., 2015; Verdugo et al.,
1065 2021). This CH₄ excess remains stored in the meltwater layer as stratification restricts downward
1066 mixing. As discussed in Damm et al. (2015), the decoupling between the deeper ocean and the
1067 atmosphere reduces the sink capacity of the Arctic Ocean.

1068 Likely sources of methane were sea ice (av. of 14 ± 5 nmol L⁻¹) and the favorable conditions for
1069 biogenic methane production, also corroborated by the microbial community data that suggested

1070 potential for methanogenesis, by detecting methanogenic archaea Thermoplasmatales (see
1071 chapter 8). The average methane concentrations in the melt pond at 10 cm depth (within the
1072 meltwater) showed values $> 20 \text{ nmol L}^{-1}$, whereas in the lead meltwater layer at the same depth
1073 the gas concentrations measured an average of $12 \pm 5 \text{ nmol L}^{-1}$. While the CH_4 excess in lead
1074 meltwater layers could translate into a significant water-to-air flux, coupling of incubation
1075 experiments performed during MOSAiC to *in-situ* measurements and microbial community
1076 structure analysis suggested potential microbial methane oxidation within the relatively fresh
1077 meltwater down to 50 cm depth, likely inhibiting CH_4 emissions into the atmosphere. The
1078 methane oxidation rate constant was in the range of 0.0003 to 0.004 d^{-1} and we did not record
1079 any negative values, suggesting prevailing methanotrophy (i.e., bacterial use of CH_4 as a source
1080 of carbon and of energy) in the upper 2 m of the open water leads. Within in-situ waters, no clear
1081 evidence of methanotrophs was detected in the most abundant fraction (see Section 8); however,
1082 the microbial community within the experimental samples could have shifted over time, giving
1083 the opportunity for CH_4 oxidizers to dominate at the end of the incubation experiment. Previous
1084 studies (e.g., Mau et al., 2013) have also reported elevated methane oxidation activity in marine
1085 environments, coincident with high CH_4 concentrations. This suggests that the CH_4 oxidizers
1086 may be able to rapidly increase oxidation rates in response to the food source abundance. As
1087 with other gases, direct flux measurements performed during MOSAiC (Shupe et al., 2022) will
1088 allow verification of this hypothesis in future work.

1089

1090 9.5 DMS

1091

1092 Dimethylsulfoniopropionate (DMSP) is the primary precursor of the climatically important gas
1093 DMS (Simó, 2001), which has been suggested as a climate regulator as it contributes to
1094 secondary aerosol formation through new particle formation and condensational growth in the
1095 atmosphere (Park et al. 2021). DMS is the most significant source of non-sea-salt (NSS) sulfate
1096 aerosol (27 Tg S yr^{-1} globally; Hulswar et al., 2021), and is an important source of aerosol
1097 particles in the summertime Arctic. This has far-reaching implications in a region where cloud
1098 formation is limited by the lack of aerosols acting as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) or ice
1099 nucleating particles (INPs). The radiative forcing effects of Arctic clouds are thus sensitive to the
1100 number of available CCN and INPs in such conditions (Mauritsen et al., 2011; Carslaw et al.,
1101 2013).

1102

1103 DMSP is an osmolyte, cryoprotectant and anti-oxidant (Stefels, 2000) produced throughout the
1104 marine microbial community (McParland & Levine, 2019; Curson et al., 2017). In polar regions,
1105 DMSP production is generally closely associated with sea ice melt events (Galindo et al., 2015;
1106 Gourdal et al., 2018; Lizotte et al., 2020; Stefels et al., 2018; Trevena & Jones, 2006), but current
1107 understanding of longer term summer processes and the drivers of DMSP and DMS turnover are
1108 poorly understood, in large part due to sampling limitations of ship-board CTD rosette systems
1109 compared to the smaller scale of the meltwater layers (e.g., Galí & Simó, 2010; Lizotte et al.,
1110 2020; Matrai et al., 2008). Gourdal et al. (2018) found a positive relationship between DMS and
1111 salinity within Arctic Ocean melt ponds, with the implication that the low salinity water did not
1112 sufficiently maintain the microbial community to support DMSP production or subsequent
1113 turnover to DMS. This was supported by Park et al. (2019), who suggested that DMS was

1114 concentrated in brackish low salinity melt ponds which had melted through. Otherwise,
1115 measurements of DMS and DMSP within the meltwater environment are very limited.

1116
1117 MOSAiC observations suggest that the presence of a meltwater layer limits emissions of DMS
1118 into the atmosphere. Concentrations of DMS(P) in surface melt ponds during both the melting
1119 and freezing seasons showed lower concentrations of both compounds in the meltwater,
1120 associated with salinities <5, compared to order of magnitude higher values below the halocline
1121 (**Figures 16 and 17**Error! Reference source not found.). This trend was mirrored in the
1122 surrounding lead waters, alongside observations of increased particulate material trapped beneath
1123 the stratification. While it is beyond the scope of this review to determine the producers and
1124 drivers of surface water turnover for DMS and other biogenic gases, it is likely that DMSP was
1125 produced during July by marine primary producers (indicated by high Chl *a*), and associated
1126 with ice melt (Stefels et al. 2018), resulting in release of DMS. While DMSP concentrations
1127 were approximately constant into August and September (Webb et al. in prep), DMS
1128 concentrations at this later time of the year were much lower than in July (**Figures 16 and 17**),
1129 suggesting very limited flux of sulfur into the atmosphere, even without the limitations of the
1130 meltwater. These results give weight to the hypothesis of a limited water-to-air DMS flux in the
1131 Central Arctic. While autumn meltwater mixing and breakdown of the stratified layer could
1132 potentially release DMS towards the atmosphere, this process occurred at the time when surface
1133 ice was thickening, further limiting atmospheric flux (see Sections 6). While there is indirect
1134 evidence of a limited water-to-air DMS flux in the Central Arctic (e.g., low atmospheric levels of
1135 DMS and its oxidation products in the Central Arctic, or concentration spikes due to transport
1136 from the Marginal Ice Zone (Baccarini et al., 2020; Schmale and Baccarini, 2021; Zhang et al.,
1137 2022)), direct flux measurements performed during the MOSAiC expedition by eddy covariance
1138 and dynamic/static flux chamber systems (Shupe et al., 2022) will confirm or deny this
1139 hypothesis. Further studies are also needed to evaluate implications for other aerosol precursors,
1140 such as iodic acid, which may be associated with sea ice processes (M. Boyer, personal
1141 communication).

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1143 9.6 Aerosols

1144
1145 The presence of a meltwater layer likely also affects primary emissions of CCN and INPs.
1146 Primary sea spray aerosol (SSA), namely sea salt, microbial cells and fragments (e.g., bacteria,
1147 viruses, and algae), and organic matter generated from marine biota (e.g., proteins, saccharides,
1148 lipids, fatty acids), and enzymes encompassing extracellular polymeric substances that can
1149 assemble into gels can be emitted directly into the atmosphere via bubble bursting and wave
1150 breaking production of airborne film, jet, and spume drops (Decho et al., 2017; Malfatti et al.,
1151 2019; Leck and Bigg, 2005a; Richter and Veron, 2016; Quinn et al., 2015). These particulate
1152 materials are often enriched in the surface microlayer (SML, the uppermost organic layer with
1153 submicrometer thickness; Bigg et al., 2004; Jayarathne et al, 2016; Leck and Bigg, 2005) and can
1154 serve as CCN (Leck and Bigg, 2005b; Christiansen et al., 2020; Orellana et al., 2011), giant CCN
1155 (Barahona et al, 2010; Jensen et al., 2017), and/or INPs (Bigg, 1996; Creamean et al., 2019;
1156 DeMott et al., 2016; Knopf et al., 2011; Mitts et al., 2021; Wilson et al., 2015; Wolf et al., 2019).
1157 Conditions for wind-driven SSA emission are generally ubiquitous in the global oceans, but pack
1158 ice and meltwater sources are unique to the polar regions and add complexity to SSA
1159 composition, abundance, and cloud-relevant properties. Only limited studies on SSA generation

1160 from leads in pack ice are available, which at this stage report conflicting results (Held et al.,
1161 2011; Kirpes et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2022). Wind is typically weak in the summertime Arctic
1162 (Shupe et al., 2022), when marine biological productivity peaks, limiting the emission of
1163 aerosols from whitecaps and waves. In addition, the presence of very low clouds in the summer,
1164 which were frequent during leg 4 of the MOSAiC expedition, might provide a wet deposition
1165 sink for aerosols. Even fewer studies have evaluated primary aerosol emissions from relatively-
1166 fresh melt ponds; those few have suggested that melt ponds may be a source of biological aerosol
1167 that serve as INPs, likely from melt pond SMLs (Creamean et al., 2022; Hartmann et al., 2021;
1168 Zeppenfeld et al., 2019). Depending on nutrient availability, the productivity of bacteria, algae,
1169 grazers, and higher trophic level organisms in meltwater can be prolific (Mundy et al., 2011;
1170 Sorensen et al., 2017), and thus, could serve as meltwater sources of primary particulate material
1171 that becomes airborne via bubble bursting or under windier conditions. Yet, this is complicated
1172 by the fact that: (1) fresher water sources tend to reduce production of SSA compared to more
1173 saline waters (Zinke et al., 2022) and (2) meltwater from snow or sea ice have disparate and
1174 diverse microbiological communities, meaning they could generate different types of airborne
1175 materials. Evidence from MOSAiC suggests that melt ponds can be sources of primary
1176 biological aerosols and INPs (Creamean et al., 2022); however, the exchange of such particles
1177 across the air-water interface might have been limited as subnivean ponds (i.e., pooling of
1178 meltwater beneath lingering snow on the ice surface) evolved into highly stratified melt ponds
1179 and meltwater layers on top of open leads (Webster et al., 2022). Future work is needed to better
1180 constrain the impact of meltwater layer characteristics and their contribution to primary aerosol
1181 CCN and INPs, particularly at a time of year when aerosol concentrations could be significantly
1182 influenced by meltwater processes.

1183 1184 9.7 Summary 1185

1186 Together, recent observations suggest that changes in the high biomass layer trapped directly
1187 below the meltwater layer throughout the melt season result in changes to biogenic gas
1188 production, but there is no unifying trend in concentration profiles across the gases. This is
1189 unsurprising given the different production and consumption pathways of oxygen, carbon, sulfur,
1190 and nitrogen, both biotic and abiotic. However, the MOSAiC dataset allows them to be
1191 compared side by side in the meltwater for the first time. Much of the existing data on processes
1192 involving these key elements has focused on the Canadian Archipelago or around Svalbard, with
1193 very little in the Central Arctic or other areas of pack ice. Further work to understand the
1194 dynamics of the large, pack-ice areas that dominate the Arctic is essential to understand
1195 elemental cycling on the basin scale. Evidence of the impact of meltwater on gas/aerosol cycling
1196 in the literature has largely focused on melt ponds, applying a simple open or closed model,
1197 which observations from MOSAiC have shown cannot be broadly applied. While it has been
1198 suggested that some gases may have a direct relationship of concentration with water salinity,
1199 higher resolution data across a range of conditions would allow testing this hypothesis. We
1200 additionally suggest investigation into the capacity for gas production within thin meltwater
1201 layers (as indicated by CH₄), which would further impact concentrations of other gases in the
1202 surface layer beyond atmosphere dissolution. Finally, it is not known to what degree the
1203 meltwater layer acts as a permeable barrier 1) with the ocean below, such that there may be
1204 diffusion of gases from the underlying water column or whether upward fluxes into the
1205 meltwater layer are driven by mixing alone, and 2) with the atmosphere.

1206

1207 10. Effects of climate change

1208 The anticipated future changes in the location and prevalence of meltwater layers depend on a
1209 number of factors. This especially includes the meltwater flux from the ice to the ocean during
1210 the melt season (April-July). We use CESM2 (Danabasoglu et al., 2020), a CMIP6 fully-coupled
1211 climate model, to visualize the trend in snow and sea ice meltwater input over the next century
1212 given different climate change scenarios (**Figure 18**). In all scenarios, the meltwater flux is
1213 expected to decrease around the margins and increase in the central Arctic Basin. In the “best
1214 case” SSP1-2.6 and “moderate future pathway” SSP3-7.0, the majority of the area is expected to
1215 trend towards more meltwater input than at present. In the “high-emissions” SSP5-8.5, there is
1216 almost no area that would be expected to have increasing meltwater input as the extent of sea ice
1217 cover is greatly reduced. A more seasonal sea ice cover in the Central Arctic results in more melt
1218 locally and less around the margins where there will be no more ice. We note that “freshwater”
1219 from sea-ice melt is more likely to remain in the Arctic compared to fresh meltwater from other
1220 sources, such as Greenland ice sheet melt, due primarily to the spatial distribution of such fluxes
1221 (e.g., Zanowski et al. 2021).

1222

1223 **Figure 18. Projected future trends in Arctic summer snow and sea-ice meltwater flux.** Estimated projected trend
1224 in total April-July meltwater flux m/yr from 2015-2101 for three future scenarios SSP1-2.6, SSP3-7.0, and SSP5-8.5
1225 from the CESM2 runs contributed to CMIP6. The meltwater flux shows a pattern of increases in the Central Basin
1226 with decreases in the margins for all scenarios, but with the area of increased flux decreasing in higher emissions
1227 scenarios.

1228 Of course, the propensity for the meltwater input to form thin, stratified layers as described in
1229 this manuscript depends on other factors including sea ice morphology and concentration, and
1230 wind and drift speed, which are also likely to change in future scenarios. Thinning ice (Kwok et
1231 al., 2015) and accelerated ice motion (Rampal et al., 2011; Itkin et al., 2017) may reduce the
1232 potential for meltwater layers spatially in the future. Additionally, the Arctic is trending towards
1233 more seasonally ice-covered areas that support wave generation in the summer (i.e., Stopa et al.
1234 2016), which may increase surface mixing and reduce the potential for stratification to form
1235 when ice concentrations are low.

1236

1237 Sea ice microbial communities can act as seeding stocks for the meltwater community,
1238 influencing both the taxonomic and metabolic diversity of the associated microbial communities
1239 present in meltwater habitats. Thinner ice may also support earlier development of phototrophic
1240 biomass in spring due to larger light transmission through thinner ice and snow cover (Nicolaus
1241 et al. 2012). Thinning ice could therefore change the bloom timing, composition and biomass
1242 levels of both sympagic and pelagic algae (Olsen et al. 2017). Shifting biodiversity could further

1243 influence biogeochemical cycling within meltwater layers, including compounds that play key
1244 roles in climate feedbacks (Edwards et al. 2020). Meanwhile, the environmental conditions in
1245 this habitat including salinity, irradiance, and nutrients are subject to change, with corresponding
1246 changes in physiology and productivity. In a more dynamic Arctic, one may expect both more
1247 frequent occurrence, but also the erosion of such layers, possibly increasing the potential for
1248 pulsed sinking events with efficient carbon export to depth.

1249
1250 Current models project increasing magnitudes of DMS, CO₂, N₂O and CH₄ fluxes in the Arctic
1251 as a result of increased open water area (Galí et al., 2019; 2021; Levasseur, 2013; Parmentier et
1252 al., 2013; Kitidis et al., 2010). However, if open water in areas of partial ice cover is covered by
1253 a meltwater layer of different gas concentration with respect to that in under-ice water (see Sect.
1254 9), the magnitude of the fluxes will be significantly different, as observed in stratified coastal
1255 waters (Miller et al., 2019). Gas exchange rates and concentrations are thus likely to rely on the
1256 relative timing of peak production and melting, due to limited exchange through a stable
1257 meltwater layer. In a more distant future, as sea ice declines and the extent of the stable
1258 meltwater layer gradually diminishes, air-sea gas and aerosol exchanges could indeed increase
1259 substantially, leading to profound impacts on the emissions and uptake of climate-relevant gases
1260 and cloud-forming aerosols. In addition to increased air-sea gas exchange, the biogenic
1261 production of DMS, N₂O and CH₄ may also increase under scenarios with less sea ice coverage
1262 (Uhlig et al., 2019) either through the direct release of DMSP or through a shift in the onset of
1263 phytoplankton blooms (Vancoppenolle et al., 2013; Kurosaki et al., 2022). All current air-sea gas
1264 transfer models, both empirical and physical, assume a well-mixed ocean surface layer. It is
1265 clear these cannot be applied an open water environment with strong surface stratification.
1266 Global climate models, which rely on existing measurements and calculations of fluxes, require
1267 further research to take into account the impact of thin, meltwater layers during the summer in a
1268 rapidly changing Arctic.

1269 11. Conclusion: challenges and future directions

1270 During the melt season, snow-and sea ice-derived meltwaters can accumulate under quiescent
1271 conditions in leads and under-ice, resulting in strongly stratified layers on the order of 1 m
1272 situated directly at the interface between sea ice, ocean, and atmosphere. A key outcome of this
1273 review manuscript and the new observations from MOSAiC is an acknowledgement of the far-
1274 reaching implications of meltwater layers for nearly every component of the Arctic coupled
1275 system. Meltwater layers have been previously observed in most regions of the Arctic Basin.
1276 Some of the major impacts include:

- 1277 • The presence of meltwater layers can impact the icescape, in particular by resulting in the
1278 formation of false bottoms under the ice or even in leads. A proposal submitted to include this
1279 and other melt-related terminology in the WMO Sea Ice Nomenclature (JCOMM Expert Team on
1280 Sea Ice, 2014) would help support more standardized observation and discussion of these unique
1281 features.
- 1282 • The strong stratification has large implications for the distribution of absorbed solar energy, and
1283 the concentration of heat within meltwater layers can result in temperatures well above the
1284 salinity-dependent freezing temperature and melt rates above the local average (see **Figure 7**;
1285 **Figure 8**). Trapping of particles and organisms within the meltwater layer can increase the
1286 turbidity and further increase the solar absorption.

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- The strong stratification between the meltwater layer and the underlying ocean acts as a barrier to reduce vertical momentum fluxes from the atmosphere to the ocean (similar to sea ice). The high buoyancy of the meltwater layer requires considerable energy to mix downwards. Consequently, most of the wind-induced turbulence is trapped within the meltwater layer such that dissipation rates may be 1-2 orders of magnitude lower in the upper meters of the ocean than in the absence of a meltwater layer (e.g., **Figure 11**).
 - Meltwater stratification serves as a physiological barrier for biological growth and migration, and the exchange of nutrients and organic matter between habitable environments – thus impacting organismal diversity, distributions, and productivity. Further investigating and identifying the key ecological processes that are impacted by, and coupled to, this meltwater input will be critical to predicting and modeling future change in Arctic Ocean biodiversity and consequences for higher trophic levels.
 - Evidence from the repeated meltwater sampling during MOSAiC suggest that the meltwater layer has at least as strong of a capping effect as previously proposed for the sea ice cover. With the increasing rate of sea ice loss across the Arctic Ocean as a whole, and changing duration and coverage of meltwater during the polar summer, existing estimates of gas and aerosol fluxes are likely to be significantly over or under-estimated (e.g., Miller et al., 2019). Due to the biogenic nature of many of the gases and aerosols studied here, changes to the ecology and productivity across the Arctic will likely also have significant effects on gas and aerosol production and projections by climate models.

1307

1308 The sparsity of observations of these layers are a reflection of the inadequacy of traditional

1309 methods for capturing this layer and its impacts (e.g. Miller et al., 2019), rather than the rarity of

1310 these layer themselves. As such, the development of technology that is better suited for

1311 observing such small-scale mm-cm features over greater spatial and temporal scales is a key

1312 challenge for the future. Autonomous instruments offer opportunities for increasing

1313 observational capacity. New ice-tethered profilers are able to profile to within a few centimeters

1314 of the ice bottom, including a new generation of Ice-Tethered Profilers (ITP) that profile closer

1315 to the surface than before and are able to survive in open water (Toole et al., 2011), and the D-

1316 TOP buoy designed by the Ocean University of China. Additionally, new methods are in

1317 development to expand the capability of ice-mass-balance buoys IMBs by pairing conductivity

1318 cells that will allow identification of under-ice meltwater layers (I. Raphael, personal

1319 communication). Electromagnetic methods have been used to detect fresh under-ice river plumes

1320 (Prinsenberg et al., 2008) and may allow detection of low-conductivity meltwater layers beneath

1321 the ice on the large-scale. These detailed in situ measurements could then help guide focused

1322 discrete sampling of the relatively thin meltwater layers to be able to compare data from a wide

1323 range of physical, chemical, and biological measurements to the interface and seawater layers

1324 below.

1325

1326 While there is motivation to continue to move towards autonomous instrumentation, which

1327 increases the possibility for higher spatial and temporal coverage, the gap in our ability to

1328 observe these features with clarity currently motivates on-ice process studies. Further

1329 development of instruments that profile while rising upwards is promising for capturing near-

1330 surface or near-ice layers (Fer et al., 2022a; M. Hoppmann, personal communication). Another

1331 possible direction includes the development of a floating under-ice sensor package that follows

1332 the ice bottom, such that it would follow the development of the under-ice layer in a Lagrangian
1333 manner (M. Hoppmann, personal communication). There is additionally a need for development
1334 of sensors to capture processes that are impacted by the presence of meltwater layers on the
1335 relevant mm-cm scales, including microbial and biogeochemical parameters. For example,
1336 development of sensors to measure the in-water profiles of gases including DMS and N₂O and
1337 the magnitude of the air-water flux in both melt ponds and areas of open water is needed to
1338 address gaps in understanding. Similarly, better methods to accurately collect water samples
1339 from these microscale features and their interfaces for biological measurements, without too
1340 much disturbance, should be considered for future fieldwork targeting these environments.

1341
1342 The geographic distribution and temporal persistence of such features cannot yet be determined
1343 from current observations. For example, it is unknown whether similar features can be expected
1344 to develop associated with sea ice melt in Antarctica. While the larger density difference
1345 between sea ice meltwater and underlying seawater may increase the propensity for meltwater
1346 layers to form, the relative dominance of large waves from the Southern Ocean and strong
1347 coastal winds in many regions are capable of breaking down near-surface stratification as it
1348 forms. There have been fresher surface layers indicated in observations of Antarctic coastal
1349 waters (e.g., van Leeuwe et al., 2020), but to our knowledge there have not been measurements
1350 of sufficient resolution identifying layers of the scale discussed here. Additionally, identification
1351 of the origin of meltwater lenses in Antarctic coastal regions is complicated by the large influx of
1352 ice sheet meltwater. As such, dedicated upper ocean observations during the melt season and the
1353 development of satellite remote sensing methods to capture the likely presence of meltwater
1354 layers would be extremely beneficial to determining their global prevalence and impact.

1355
1356 The work reviewed in this manuscript includes primarily process-scale observations, with some
1357 results from process-scale modeling, as climate-scale models cannot be assumed to accurately
1358 represent meltwater layers. For example, the minimum ocean surface layer thickness in many
1359 CMIP6 models is 5 – 10 m, which limits the ability to explicitly represent these layers, even
1360 though their climatic impacts could be significant. Additionally, the relationship of meltwater
1361 layers in leads and under-ice with other emergent variables such as melt pond coverage is not
1362 well-defined, such that a parameterization is not yet feasible. Thus, in order to represent these
1363 processes in both process and large-scale models, it is necessary to refine our understanding of
1364 the meltwater layer evolution and controls, and likely to implement higher model vertical
1365 resolution near the surface interface or appropriate sub-grid-scale parameterizations. This may
1366 allow additional constraints for atmospheric models, where the presence of meltwater layers
1367 significantly affects fluxes from the ocean to the atmosphere. Similarly, biogeochemical models
1368 in development using new findings from the MOSAiC expedition may better constrain fluxes of
1369 gases and nutrients based on impacts of these layers (Fong et al., in prep).

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2339 Competing interests

2340 The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

2341 Supplemental material

2342 The supplemental file (.doc) includes supplemental materials as follows:

2343 Text S1 Methods for VMP upper-ocean turbulence (Figure 10)

2344 Text S2 Methods for section 8 (organism diversity and community structure)

2345 Text S3 Methods for section 9 (air-sea gas exchange)

2346 Data accessibility statement

2347 All data plotted in this manuscript are extracted from much larger data sets that must be made
2348 publicly available prior to January 1, 2023, on the MOSAiC archives, including PANGAEA
2349 <https://www.pangaea.de/>, the National Science Foundation’s Arctic Data Center
2350 <http://arcticdata.io>, and elsewhere. The following data used in this manuscript are currently
2351 publicly available:

- 2352 • MSS: <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.939816>
- 2353 • VMP: <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.946076>
- 2354 • YSI and Castaway near-surface ocean measurements: doi:10.18739/A2TT4FV1G.
- 2355 • Mass balance transect data include melt pond depths:
2356 <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.937781>
- 2357 • Autonomous SIMBA measurements at FYI (2019T66) are available at [https://doi.pangaea.](https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.938134)
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- 2359 • Amplicon sequence data: NCBI PRJNA895866

2360 Prior to public release, direct access to data included in this manuscript can be granted by
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